

EJP SOIL
European Joint Programme

Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Deliverable D3.4

Evaluation of soil threats and ecosystem service evolution under climate, land use or management changes

Due date of deliverable: 30.08.2024
Actual submission date: 15.10.2024

GENERAL DATA

Grant Agreement: 862695

Project acronym: EJP SOIL

Project title: Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils

Project website: www.ejpsoil.eu

Start date of the project: February 1st, 2020

Project duration: 60 months

Name of lead contractor: INRAE

Funding source: H2020-SFS-2018-2020 / H2020-SFS-2019-1

Type of action: European Joint Project COFUND

DELIVERABLE NUMBER:	D3.4
DELIVERABLE TITLE:	Evaluation of soil threats and ecosystem service evolution under climate, land use or management changes
DELIVERABLE TYPE:	Report/ORDP/Website/Ethics
WORK PACKAGE N:	WP3
WORK PACKAGE TITLE:	Forecasting bundles at MS scale
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL:	CO/PU

ABSTRACT

Based on an intensive literature review (Saccamacca et al., STOTEN under review) and results from previous experiences in member states a scenario framework was developed (climate, land use, and management changes) and common methodologies (statistical methods, simple and/or more sophisticated models) were identified, used or validated to forecast how selected soil ecosystem services (SES) and soil threats (ST) will change according to climate, land-use and management changes. In contrast to WP5 we focus in WP3/Task 3 on forecasts of changes of various soil indicators on site, regional or national scale, and could rely on soil maps with high resolution that are maintained by several member states. Due to the lack of available methods/models, missing experience by member states or the availability of input data no forecasts could be done for the SES environmental pollution control, habitat for biodiversity and pest and disease control and soil contamination, loss of diversity and salinization. For **Austria** the STs soil erosion and nutrient imbalances and the SESs soil erosion regulation, greenhouse gas regulation and carbon sequestration as well as primary biomass production are modelled and mapped. We used RUSLE for the simulation of changes in soil erosion in arable land at national scale and the biogeochemical model Landscape DNDC for the other and SES and ST for 5 representative regions in Austria by applying 2 climate change scenarios, various management scenarios to fulfil parts of the EU green deal and did a regional analysis of the LUISA land use change from the LUISA modelling platform. In Austria we had the possibility to use high resolution soil maps and daily climate data. In the **Czech Republic**, soil compaction was quantified under different land use and climate change scenarios which offers insights into future environmental and agricultural challenges. In the climate change scenarios, intense land use change are the drivers that may influence also the change in bulk density. The same methods as used in WP5 were applied. In **Estonia** the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios were used to assess the SES of GHG and climate regulation. The scenarios were developed using the GHG Cookbook's NEP (Net Ecosystem Productivity) calculations from the SERENA project, which incorporate MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) terrestrial primary production products, along with climatic variables in spatially explicit databases. The NEP was assessed based on projections of average temperature and soil moisture for the RCP scenarios, assuming that the MODIS inputs remain stable. The second study assessed the impact of winter cropping systems on long-term soil fertility and the potential to mitigate Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) loss. Using an SOC stock map for Estonian mineral arable soils, developed by the Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge, SOC stock projections were conducted for two contrasting land management scenarios—bare soil during the winter months and continuous vegetation, over the 2020–2040 period, using the RothC model. Carbon inputs were estimated based on crop yields and manure production data specific to the study area, covering the years 2015–2020. In **France** changes in various SES's were calculated in two contrasting areas which differ in terms of their environmental characteristics (soil, climate), their past and present agricultural production systems, and also in terms of their territorial dynamics. The approach used to construct and evaluate scenarios for these areas was identical on both sites and focused on studying changes in 12 indicators of 4 categories of SES (biomass/primary production, greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration, hydrological control and environmental pollution control) and 1 ST (soil sealing). The scenario analysis in **Ireland** explores the potential to reduce soil compaction in Ireland's arable agricultural land through the adoption of zero tillage (ZT) and cover cropping (CC). Soil compaction, a significant form of soil degradation in Europe and across the globe, negatively impacts soil structure by increasing density and reducing pore space, which hampers plant growth, water infiltration, and ecosystem functioning. This

analysis relies on literature-based values for BD reductions. **Poland:** For the evaluation of the climate change scenarios the time frames: 2018, 2030, 2050, and 2100 and the three Global Circulation Models (GCMs) were used that were calibrated according to the Polish climate data. These GCMs were as following: (i) MPI-M-ESM-LR, (ii) ICHEC – EC- EARTH, (iii) IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR. Monthly means were selected for the timeframes for minimal and maximal temperature, and precipitation.

For the analysis of the land use changes the LUISA data for 2050 were used to analyse the land use classes changes corresponding to the CORINE Land Cover Level 3 classes. Data was used as a C factor for the soil erosion soil threat and soil erosion control for the soil-based ecosystem service. After the investigation of the data and preliminary analysis of the SOC change according to the different agricultural management practices it was decided to exclude this data due to not achieving any clear changes for these scenarios. The data used in this part of the task was collected from approximately 500 farms in Poland from 2019 to 2022. In each year farmers provided the information of the cultivation practices, fertilizers used, crops, yields, the area of the field from which we collected sample, and the soil properties of the field.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	Work Package
EU	European Union
ST	Soil threat
SES	Soil ecosystem Service
GHG	Greenhouse gas
AT	Austria
CZ	Czech Republic
EE	Estonia
FR	France
IE	Ireland
PL	Poland

1. Introduction

Our soils are the most important providers of numerous ecosystem services (ES) but can react very sensitive to factors such as changes in climate, land use, land management and land cover. The question of how we can avoid threats to our soils in the future, or how we can maintain or, in the best case, improve different soil ecosystem functions that soils fulfil can be assessed with the help of simulation models and scenario analyses. In the recent decades, different soil models have been developed, which pose great challenges to the modelling of soil processes due to the complexity of soils and their importance for the broad spectrum of ecosystem services.

The objective of Task 3.3. was to evaluate soil threats (ST) and soil-based ecosystem services (SES) according to different climate change, land use/cover and management scenarios on local, regional or national scale. In order to assess the possible dynamics of bundles of SES and ST in the frame of climate change and/or different land use/management, a modelling approach was needed and herein used. The methodological approaches for soil threats and ecosystem services modelling were dependent on the target scale(s) in each country and the available data of the member states. To do so, several milestones were needed and delivered to reach the goals of the project proposal.

- For **milestone 3.4** we reviewed existing modelling studies focusing on SES and ST including climate change, land use change and management scenarios. A publication has been submitted to “Science of the total environment” and is currently being reviewed. The title of the manuscript is: Assessing and mapping soil ecosystem services and soil threats changes in agroecosystems through scenario-based approaches – a systematic review.
- To evaluate various SES and ST at member state level we first selected the most important SES and ST and decided on applicable models (**milestone 3.6**) that can be used to fulfil the proposed deliverable.
- For **milestone 3.7** we founded a working group to develop a scenario framework for all participating member states. Member states that were able to run scenario analyses were Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Ireland and Poland.
- For **milestone 3.8** we developed a list of forecasts about the ST and SES and bundles that can be modelled in each MS.
- For **deliverable 3.4** we finally deliver here the evaluation of soil threats/ ES evolution under climate and/or land use/management changes.

2. Methods

The most important SES and ST per member state that could be simulated are shown in Table 1. Three countries out of 6 were able to give predictions for changes on the SES “GHG and climate regulation”. Two countries were working on the SES “Primary biomass production” and could predict changes in “Erosion control” on a national scale. “Hydrological control” and “Environmental pollution control” was predicted in one country in 2 regions. Changes in climate, land management or land use change and their effects on ST could be predicted less often. Three countries could predict the effects of changes on “Soil organic carbon loss” and on “Soil compaction”, two countries estimated the loss of soil via erosion. Only one country each could predict effects of changes on “Soil nutrient imbalance” and “Soil acidification” and “Soil sealing” Either no appropriate model or no experience was available for the SES “Habitat for biodiversity” and “Pest and disease control” and for the ST’s “Waterlogging”, “Soil contamination”, “Loss of diversity” and “Salinization”. In Table 2 the scenarios, methods and scale of mapping are listed.

Table 1: Soil ecosystem services (SES) and soil threats (ST) simulated by the member states. AT= Austria, CZ= Czech Republic, EE= Estonia, FR=France, IE=Ireland, PL=Poland.

		AT	CZ	EE	FR	IE	PL	No.
Soil ecosystem service (SES)								
Primary/biomass production	ES_Prod	x			x			2
Greenhouse gas and climate regulation (including carbon sequestration)	ES_GHG	x		x	x			3
Hydrological control (purification, supply, regulation)	ES_Hydr				x			1
Erosion control	ES_Eros	x					x	2
Environmental pollution control (e.g. filtration, buffering or sequestration of harmful substances)	ES_Poll							
Habitat for biodiversity	ES_Biod							
Pest and disease control	ES_Pest							
Soil threats (ST)								
Nutrient imbalance (macronutrients, micronutrients, deficiency/excess)	ST_Nutr	x						1
Soil organic carbon loss	ST_Carb	x		x			x	3
Waterlogging	ST_Wate							
Soil erosion (water, wind, tillage)	ST_Eros	x					x	2
Soil contamination (e.g. potentially toxic elements, organic pollutants)	ST_Cont							
Loss of diversity (plants, fungi, bacteria, microarthropods, enchytraeids; potential metabolic diversity, etc.)	ST_Biod							
Soil acidification	ST_Acid						x	1
Salinization	ST_Sali							
Soil sealing	ST_Seal	x						1
Soil compaction	ST_Comp		x			x	x	3

Table 2 : Climate change, management and land use change scenarios performed by the countries Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Ireland and Poland sorted by scale (local, regional, national) and soil ecosystem services (SES) and soil threats (ST).

acronym	Member state	Model/method	Climate change			Management			Landuse change		
			local	regional	national	local	regional	national	local	regional	national
ST_Seal	Austria	SERENA Cookbook								1	
ST_Eros/ES E		RUSLE, R cookbook from SERENA			X			X			-
ST_Carb		LandscapeDN DC			5			5			
ES_GHG					5			5			
ES_Nutr					5				5		
ES_Prod					5				5		
ST_Comp	Czech Republic	DSM, Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) algorithm			X						X
ES_GHG	Estonia	GHG cookbook NEP		1							
ST_Carb		RothC					1				
ES_Hydr	France	STICS	2			1			2		
ES_GHG			2			2			2		
ES_Prod			2			2			2		
ST_Comp	Ireland	literature review, estimation						X			
ST_Eros, ES_Eros	Poland	RUSLE, SERENA cookbook, LUISA	1		X						X
ST_Carb, ES_GHG		DSM, Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) algorithm			X						X
ST_Acid					X						X
ST_Comp					X						X

Climate change scenarios:

Within the working group “Scenarios” we decided to use RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 climate change scenarios and up to 5 different global climate models. Czech Republic was using SSP climate change scenarios. Scenario runs were done until 2050 or 2100. More details on Scenarios and used models is given below under the country specific results.

Land management scenarios:

Green deal

For the land management scenarios, we followed the proposed scenarios defined in the Green Deal and implemented some of the measures already suggested in the latest Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). For our purposes the below mentioned points were most relevant for the countries and could be best simulated with the available models and methods.

- Reduce the loss of nutrients from fertilisers by 50%, resulting in the reduction of fertilizer use by at least 20%; reduce nutrient losses by at least 50%, while ensuring that there is no deterioration in soil fertility
- Legally protect a minimum of 30% of the EU’s land area and 30% of the EU’s sea area; Strictly protect at least a third of the EU’s protected areas - representing 10% of the EU land and 10% of EU sea;
- to enhance biodiversity in agricultural land that would contribute to conserving and increasing soil organic carbon (SOC);
- Ensure that at least 10% of agricultural area is under high-biodiversity landscape features
- reduction of GHG emissions to at least 55% below 1990 levels by 2030 (keep the global temperature increase to well below 2°C and pursue efforts to keep it to 1.5°C); reach net removals of 310 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent by 2030;
- keep the global temperature increase to well below 2°C and pursue efforts to keep it to 1.5°C;
- Achieve a climate-neutral Europe and, as the first step, aim to achieve land-based climate neutrality in the EU by 2035;
- Develop a long-term vision for sustainable carbon cycles (including capture, storage, and use of CO₂) in a climate-neutral EU economy
- Reach good ecological and chemical status in surface waters and good chemical and quantitative status in groundwater by 2027
- At least 25% of the EU’s agricultural land under organic farming by 2030;
- Place at least 25% of agricultural land under organic farming management, and significantly increase the uptake of agro-ecological practices.
- reduce the use of fertilisers by at least 20% by 2030;
- reduce overall EU sales of antimicrobials for farmed animals and in aquaculture by 50% by 2030
- Reach no net land take
- Propose legally binding EU restoration targets by 2021, and restore significant areas of degraded and carbon rich ecosystems by 2030; to limit drainage of wetlands and organic soils and to restore managed and drained peatlands, in order to maintain and increase soil carbon stocks, minimise flooding and drought risks, and enhance biodiversity;

3. Summary of scenarios, results and recommendations:

In the following tables (Tab. 3 and 4) the results and recommendations of all participating member states are summarized.

Table 3: SES and ST sorted by member state, used methods/models

acronym	Member state	arable/grassland	indicator	CC	management	LU	results	recommendation	
ST_Seal	Austria	A/G	sealed area (ha)	-	-	LUISA	In sum no net loss of agricultural land (compensation).	CC scenarios should be incorporated in LUISA	
ST_Eros, ES_Eros		A	annual average soil loss (t·ha ⁻¹ ·yr ⁻¹), R factor	RCP4.5, RCP8.5; 2021-2040, 2041-2060, 2061-2080	-		No general trend visible. Both increase and decrease in soil loss under RCP 4.5 and 8.5 which depend on the region. Simplified calculations used for this task, difficult to extrapolate into the future.	Crop rotations will be different in the future and could not be included. Less simplified methods needed for realistic estimations.	
ST_Carb, ES_Carb		G		SOC stock [kg C ha ⁻¹]	RCP 4.5; RCP 8.5 2026-2035; 2046-2055; 2065-2075	conventional; conventional-reduced; organic		Soil type and region depended SOC content. Increase in SOC with climate change. Decrease in reduced and organic management	Uncertainty in RCP 8.5 increase extremely. Region and soil type specific results. High resolution soil data (actual) needed , especially in a small scale agriculture like in Austria, and models that are capable to simulate bundles of indicators to evaluate SES and ST are important to get realistic forecasts in changes in SES and ST in the future. However more measurements are needed in the future to develop, improve and validate such models.
ES_GHG							Decrease and increase in N2O emissions, region depended.		
ST_Nutr							NO3 leaching decreases with climate change, region depended.		
ES_Prod							Increase in yield with climate change. Decrease under reduced and organic managements		
ST_Comp	Czech Republic	A/G	change over time in topsoil bulk density	SSP1-2.6, SSP5-8.5 scenarios until 2050	-	LUISA	Regional differences in bulk density and compaction. Clay content was the most important factor. Increasing risk of compaction in vulnerable regions. These changes could significantly impact soil health, crop productivity, and ecosystem resilience.	To reduce the risk of soil compaction in the short term, sustainable land management and conservation practices are of great importance. In the medium-term monitoring will provide the data to spot areas of high risk that need intervention. In the long-term promoting regulations and policy that limit heavy machinery usage and adaptive management practices to mitigate future risk of compaction associated with land use and climate change.	
ES_GHG	Estonia	A/G	NEP (gC m ⁻²)	RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 until 2100	-	-	Decline in NEP is mainly attributable to an expected increase in ecosystem respiration due to higher temperatures during the analyzed period	For more accurate future assessments, it is essential to incorporate detailed site-specific factors into climate change scenario analysis. The integration of terrestrial primary productivity dynamics in climate change models would enhance the precision of the projections. While data validation is needed to account for Estonia's pedoclimatic conditions, this study provides initial insights into detailed NEP modeling using climate change scenarios.	
ST_Carb			SOC stock [kg C ha ⁻¹]		winter cropping vs. bare soil		year-round vegetation can mitigate SOC loss compared to bare soil conditions during the winter months	The findings indicate that while SOC stocks are projected to decline under current practices, adopting winter cropping systems has the potential to sustain higher SOC levels , thereby enhancing soil health and contributing to agricultural sustainability.	
ES_Hydr	France	A/G	water yield (mm yr ⁻¹)	RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 until 2050	BAU, -25% less N input; organic farming; energy crop development	BAU: No change in land use from 1982 to 2050; Observed and projected urbanisation	water yield increases in all scenarios	Data processing and modelling chain developed in this project is fully operational and could be reused to test other scenarios of change or even to extend the duration of the project.	
ES_GHG			carbon storage (tC·ha ⁻¹)				carbon storage decreases in all scenarios. In organic farming it stays the same.		
ES_Prod			crop yields				no difference in organic farming and when using energy crops. Decrease when -25% N input		
ST_Comp	Ireland	A	change over time in topsoil bulk density	-	zero tillage (ZT)		Both scenarios have the potential to reduce soil compaction. Reduction in ZT are typically realised after several years,	The effectiveness depend on regional factors (soil type, climate, and the severity of existing compaction) . Other conservation techniques such as crop rotation, organic amendments, or controlled traffic farming need to be studied. Studies on long term impact are needed.	
					cover cropping (CC).		Both scenarios have the potential to reduce soil compaction. CC has a higher potential to reduce compaction and tends to show more immediate results.		

ST_Eros	Poland	A/G	annual average soil loss (t-ha ⁻¹ -yr ⁻¹)	RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 2030; 2050; 2100	LUIA	Soil erosion is predicted to increase in agricultural areas due to the climate changes, however, it can be reduced by the specific changes of land use (plantations, grassland, and orchards)	It was predicted that both land-use and climate changes have an influence on ST/SES changes. Better database on bulk density is needed due to the lowest accuracy among all the others indicators. The new regulation law is needed to protect soils from reducing their properties, and agricultural value. Biggest threat is SOC loss . SOC loss highest for the arable land, and the part of Poland currently being under the most intensive agriculture. To protect soils, more grassland should be restored as SOC will be increasing in grasslands.
ST_Carb			SOC content [%]			SOC loss is predicted to decrease in the central Poland, the more intensive agricultural activity, the more decrease of SOC. It is applied to all evaluated scenarios.	
ST_Acid			pH in water			Soil acidification is predicted to be a significant issue for the north-eastern part of Poland, where intensive agriculture is connected to the occurrence of the acidic soils.	
ES_Eros			Soil mass not eroded (t-ha ⁻¹ -yr ⁻¹)			Erosion protection will increase only on the areas currently occupied by agriculture. The change to permanent vegetation cover will significantly decrease erosion. However, climate changes may stop and worsen this process.	
ES_GHG			SOC stock [kg C ha ⁻¹]; NEP			According to the climate changes, C sequestration will decrease	

For a better readability of the main outcomes, we show here (Tab. 4) the positive (green), negative (red) or not significant effects (blue) of climate change, management or land use change on the corresponding SES or ST. In yellow, negative and positive effects were found that depend mainly on regional, soil type specific or temporal characteristics. Details on the results are shown in the member state specific parts.

Table 4 : Effects of climate change (CC), RCPs (RCP 4.5, RCP8.5), management without climate change (management wo. CC), management with climate change (management x CC - 4.5 and 8.5) and land use (LU) change on different indicators of SES or ST by country. Green = positive, red= negative, blue=no significant effects, yellow= negative and positive effects.

acronym	arable/grasland	country	indicator	management	CC - RCP 4.5	CC - RCP 8.5	management wo. CC	management x CC - 4.5	management x CC - 8.5	LU
ES_GHG	G	AT	N2O emissions [kg N ha-1]	conventional vs.conventional-reduced	yellow	yellow	green	yellow	green	
	G	AT	N2O emissions [kg N ha-1]	conventional vs. organic	yellow	yellow	green	yellow	green	
	A/G	EE	NEP (gC m-2)	-	red	red				
	A/G	FR	carbon storage (tC.ha-1)	BAU	red	red				
	A/G	FR	carbon storage (tC.ha-1)	BAU vs. -25% less N input						
	A/G	FR	carbon storage (tC.ha-1)	BAU vs. organic farming				blue	blue	
	A/G	FR	carbon storage (tC.ha-1)	BAU vs. energy crop development				red	red	
	A/G	EE	SOC stock [kg C ha-1]	bare soil vs. winter cropping			green			
	A	PL	SOC content [%]		red	red				
ST_Carb, ES_GHG	G	AT	SOC stock [kg C ha-1]	conventional vs.conventional-reduced	green	green	red	green	green	
	G	AT	SOC stock [kg C ha-1]	conventional vs. organic	green	green	red	green	green	
ES_Hydr	A/G	FR	water yield (mm yr-1)	BAU	green	green				
	A/G	FR	water yield (mm yr-1)	BAU vs. -25% less N input						
	A/G	FR	water yield (mm yr-1)	BAU vs. organic farming				green	green	
	A/G	FR	water yield (mm yr-1)	BAU vs. energy crop development				green	green	
ES_Prod	G	AT	yield [kg DW ha-1]	conventional vs.conventional-reduced	green	green	red	green	green	
	G	AT	yield [kg DW ha-1]	conventional vs. organic	green	green	red	green	green	
	A/G	FR	crop yields	BAU	green	green				
	A/G	FR	crop yields	BAU vs. -25% less N input				red	red	
	A/G	FR	crop yields	BAU vs. organic farming				blue	blue	
	A/G	FR	crop yields	BAU vs. energy crop development				blue	blue	
ST_Acid	A/G	PL	pH in water		red	red				
ST_Comp	A/G	CZ	change over time in topsoil bulk density	-	blue	blue				
	A	IE	change over time in topsoil bulk density	zero tillage (ZT)			green			
	A	IE	change over time in topsoil bulk density	cover cropping (CC)			green			
	A/G	PL	bulk density [g cm-3]		red	red				
ST_Eros, ES_Eros	A/G	PL	annual average soil loss (t·ha-1·yr-1); Soil mass not eroded (t·ha-1·yr-1)	-	red	red				green
	A/G	AT	annual average soil loss (t·ha-1·yr-1), R factor		yellow	yellow				
ST_Nutr	G	AT	NO3 leaching [kg N ha-1]	conventional vs.conventional-reduced	green	green	green	yellow	green	
	G	AT	NO3 leaching [kg N ha-1]	conventional vs. organic			green	green	yellow	
ST_Seal	A/G	AT	sealed area (ha)	-						blue

Furthermore, the following needs were specified by the member states for the future:

Most of the partners mentioned that the modeling results are soil and region specific. They recommended the usage of high-resolution soil data and the utilization of site-specific factors, long term monitoring and more studies on long-term impacts of changes on the indicators of SES and STs to validate the models. It was mentioned that less simplified methods should be used to get more realistic results. Models for bundles of SES and/or STs, models for biodiversity loss and habitat for biodiversity, pest control and pollution control need to be developed and applied for further research.

4. Country specific scenario analyses

4.1 Scenario analyses – Austria

Introduction

In Austria we assessed the soil threat (ST) **soil erosion** and **nutrient imbalance** and soil ecosystem service (SES) **soil erosion regulation** for agricultural soil in Austria and furthermore we simulated the SES **greenhouse gas regulation; carbon sequestration** and **primary biomass production** in grassland production systems in five regions of Austria.

Table 5 : AT - Soil threats and soil ecosystem services simulated in Austria.

Soil threat or soil ecosystem service	Method	Land use	Management	Climate
Soil erosion	RUSLE R cookbook	arable stay arable	no changes	RCP4.5; RCP8.5
Greenhouse gas regulation and soil C sequestration	LandscapeDNDC	grassland	non-organic intensive + biodiversity-friendly + organic	RCP4.5; RCP8.5
Soil nutrient imbalance		grassland	conventional; conventional-reduced; organic	RCP4.5; RCP8.5
Primary biomass production				
Soil sealing	Serena Cookbook	LUISA	-	-

Part 1: Soil Erosion

Methods

Soil erosion was modelled via an application of the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE, Renard et al., 1997). Simulation periods covering the time periods 2021-2040, 2041-2060 and 2061-2080. For the calculations, the R cookbook developed in SERENA was used (Coblinski, 2024), the original application as done for Task 3.2 is described in SERENA-Deliverable D3.3. The RUSLE was implemented in the following form:

$$A = C \times K \times R \times LS \times P$$

where: A: annual average soil loss (t·ha⁻¹·yr⁻¹); C: cover-management factor (dimensionless); K: soil erodibility factor (t·hm²·h·hm⁻²·MJ⁻¹·mm⁻¹); R: rainfall erosivity factor (MJ·mm·ha⁻¹·h⁻¹·yr⁻¹); LS: slope length and steepness factor (dimensionless), and P: conservation practices factor (dimensionless).

The factors of RUSLE were prepared on a 25 x 25 m² resolution, snapped to the grid of the JRC-LS-factor map and calculated according to the following procedures:

C: A lookup table for C-factors per CORINE land use class (CLC) was used. Most of the C-factors come from two tables in Panagos et al. (2015b), deviations shown in Table 6.

K: Calculation was based on a combination of European Soil Texture Data (Ballabio et al., 2016) and soil organic carbon from Wenzel et al. (2022).

R: Calculated from daily values from climate change scenario predictions. Data for the required time frames were extracted from two ensemble predictions for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. Bias corrected daily precipitation was downloaded from the Data Server of the Climate Change Center Austria (CCCA) under the EURO-CORDEX model annotations ICHEC-EC-EARTH_rcp45_r12i1p1_SMHI-RCA4 and ICHEC-EC-EARTH_rcp85_r12i1p1_SMHI-RCA4.

LS: The JRC national map for LS-factor (Panagos et al., 2015a) was used.

P: The map of Panagos et al. (2015c) and Panagos et al. (2020) was used.

Table 6 : AT - C-factor lookup table used for soil loss modelling in Task 3.2 and for the scenarios in Task 3.3.

Corine Code	C-factor	Corine Label	source
111	0.0539	urban continuous	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
112	0.0539	urban discontinuous	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
121	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
122	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
123	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
124	0.0539	industry transport etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
131	0.0539	mining landfills etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
132	0.0539	mining landfills etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
133	0.0539	mining landfills etc	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
141	0.0539	green urban areas	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
142	0.0539	sport and leisure	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
211	0.11	non-irrigated arable	(Schmaltz et al., 2023) MEAN all Austrian cropland
221	0.3403	vineyards	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
222	0.2188	fruit trees berries	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 3
231	0.0853	pastures	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
242	0.13	complex cultivation patterns	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
243	0.1211	arable with natural vegetation	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
244	0.1211	agro-forestry areas	set to same as 243
311	0.012	broad-leaved forest	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
312	0.012	coniferous forest	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
313	0.012	mixed forest	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
321	0.0345	natural grassland	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
322	0.0345	moors and heathland	set to same as 321
324	0.0215	transitional woodland shrub	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
331	0	beaches dunes sandplains	set to zero
332	0	bare rock	set to zero
333	0.2308	sparsely vegetated areas	(Panagos et al., 2015b) Table 4
335	0	glaciers perpetual snow	set to zero
411	0	inland marshes	set to zero
412	0	peatbogs	set to zero
511	0	water courses	set to zero
512	0	water bodies	set to zero

Since the modified C-factor for CLC class 333 as proposed in Task 3.2 showed minimal influence on the overall result, it was dropped from the analyses for Task 3.3, to prevent further increase in the number of scenarios. Instead, only the default value from Table 4 in (Panagos et al., 2015b) was used. The resulting soil loss rates from Task 3.2 are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 : AT - Resulting modelled soil loss rates for period 1991-2020 from modelling in Task 3.2 - this is the reference scenario for comparisons in Task 3.3.

Results

Rainfall erosivity (R-Factor)

For the scenario evaluation, erosion calculation using the cookbook methodology from Task 3.2 remained the same, only the R-factor maps were replaced with maps based on climate projections. ÖKS15 climate projections based on the two representative concentration pathways RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 were utilized. The projections cover the time range from 1951 to 2100 and have daily temporal resolution and are based on (Switanek et al., 2017) and (Hofstätter et al., 2015). Within this time range, three separate 20-year periods were considered: 2021-2040, 2041-2060 and 2061-2080. Within each period, the mean predicted monthly sums of precipitation were calculated. The resulting 12 separate rasters for each period were then used for R-factor calculation within the cookbook procedure.

Concerning climate projections, Austria seems like being split in two by the Alps with partially opposite trends on either side of this mountain range. Consequently, aggregated values at national level provide little insight. For example, the mean change in R-factor might be close to zero for one scenario, but is

in fact simply going in opposite directions north and south of the Alps. In general, the results show high spatial heterogeneity.

While some of these changes in R-factor might have dramatic influence on soil erosion happening in Austria, the largest differences occur in Alpine or Alpine foothills regions, where land-use is dominated by grassland and forest. This is indicated by including the extent of the main agricultural production zones (MAPZ) in the maps. The zones labelled HA, VA and AOR fall within this description as Alpine or foothills regions. The remaining MAPZ are currently known to show serious erosion risk and cropland - dominated. Of course, this pattern of crop- or grassland domination might see changes in the future, which we cannot assess in this task.

The scenarios from RCP4.5 show the largest increases in R-factor in the Alpine regions in the centre and far south of the map, within the MAPZs VA and AOR.

The results attained do not follow the expected sequence of increasing differences to the reference period with each time period. Instead, differences seem largest in the 2021-2040 period and smaller in the following periods. This might be due to the prediction being not perfectly aligned with the recent (1991-2020 period) measurements but showing an abrupt change in rainfall. For all three time periods, large areas show little change or a decrease in R-factor, especially in the MAPZ SFH. MAPZ AVL, which is already currently an erosion-prone area consistently shows increasing R-factor values with each time period considered. The picture is less uniform for the MAPZ WMV and NFH. WMV shows mostly a decrease or only slight increase, while the westernmost part consistently shows an increase.

The following Fig. 2 - 7 show the relative change of the calculated R-factor for each scenario compared to the R-factor for 1991-2020 calculated within the cookbook in Task 3.2. The projected changes range from - 40 % to + 250 % for some locations. In the maps, reductions are indicated with green colours and increases with yellow to red colours. For most of the area, changes are not that large, and changes of +/- 5 % are shown without colour in the figures. This 5 % threshold was chosen arbitrarily.

Figure 2 : AT - Modelled relative change of R-factor for period 2021-2040 according to RCP4.5.

Figure 3 : AT - Modelled relative change of R-factor for period 2041-2060 according to RCP4.5.

Figure 4 : AT - Modelled relative change of R-factor for period 2061-2080 according to RCP4.5.

The image looks quite different for the RCP 8.5 scenarios. Initially (2021-2040), most areas except MAPZ NFH and SFH show increases in R-factor, while increases are covering most of the total area in the two time periods further away. Still, it is not a uniform development of getting worse (i.e. higher) with each period considered. The reasons for this are probably within the intricacies of the modelling

behind the scenarios and cannot be uncovered within this task. It might be feasible not to use the measured 1991-2020 rainfall as reference, but instead the values predicted within each scenario. This was tested but would lead to another increase in the number of scenarios, using separate reference values for comparison. We found that the mean value of the 1991-2020 time periods from both projections closely matches our own calculation for 1991-2020 and decided to use only the latter as reference for comparison.

Figure 5 : AT - Modelled relative change of R-factor for period 2021-2040 according to RCP8.5.

Figure 6 : AT - Modelled relative change of R-factor for period 2041-2060 according to RCP8.5.

Figure 7 : AT - Modelled relative change of R-factor for period 2061-2080 according to RCP8.5.

Concluding from the comparisons made, we decided to keep the scenario from Task 3.2 as baseline. R-factor values calculated there are very close to the mean value of both 1991-2020 periods from the

two climate projections. Again, we tried to prevent having too many scenarios to compare, and especially using two different base values for comparison.

Soil loss rates

In a similar fashion, the modelled soil loss rates resulting when using the different R-factors were calculated and then compared to the baseline of modelled soil loss for the period 1991-2020 from Task 3.2. This is summarized in Table 7, Table 8 and the following figures. As described in the section on R-factor calculation, the focus for erosion-related purposes is on the main cropland regions, represented by the MAPZ AVL, NFH; SFH and WMV, in contrast to the remaining grassland-dominated MAPZ AOR, HA and VA.

Table 7 : AT - Mean absolute soil loss rates (t/ha.a) of the different scenarios per main agricultural production zone (MAPZ).

Scenario \ MAPZ	HA	VA	AOR	WMV	KB	AVL	SFH	NFH
Reference 1991-2020 mean	10.10	3.80	2.52	0.87	1.78	1.22	1.27	0.48
RCP4.5 1991-2020 mean	9.91	3.91	2.28	0.80	1.63	1.28	1.12	0.42
RCP4.5 2021-2040 mean	10.19	4.11	2.38	0.90	1.70	1.37	1.19	0.52
RCP4.5 2041-2060 mean	9.73	3.88	2.20	0.77	1.60	1.25	1.11	0.43
RCP4.5 2061-2080 mean	9.77	3.96	2.21	0.82	1.65	1.29	1.19	0.44
RCP8.5 1991-2020 mean	9.56	4.12	2.44	0.86	1.80	1.32	1.25	0.46
RCP8.5 2021-2040 mean	10.05	3.84	2.50	0.91	1.99	1.33	1.20	0.40
RCP8.5 2041-2060 mean	11.44	4.54	2.97	0.93	2.14	1.49	1.58	0.52
RCP8.5 2061-2080 mean	10.34	4.29	2.64	1.01	2.02	1.47	1.41	0.52

Figure 8 : AT - Absolute soil loss rates modelled for the RCP4.5 scenario.

Figure 9 : AT - Absolute soil loss rates modelled for the RCP8.5 scenario

Fig. 10 - 15 shows the relative change in modelled soil loss rates for the different scenarios. Three areas that are present in all the scenarios (centre of the map, close to the label “VA”, southernmost tip of Carinthia, Westernmost part of MAPZ VA) seem to be artifacts that show the difference between the dataset used for calculating the 1991-2020 period and the subsequently modelled climate scenarios. They show the highest relative differences but are located in grassland-dominated areas.

In the RCP 4.5 scenario for 2021-2040, reductions in soil loss rates can be seen in some areas, such as most of SFH, the central part of WMV and the eastern part of AVL. Others show increasing soil loss rates of around 10-40%, such as the western part of AVL, most of NFH, or the eastern part of SFH.

In the following time periods 2041-2060 and 2061-2080, the changes get somewhat muted and relative differences are generally lower. NFH and WMV turn mostly into slight reductions. The area’s most concerning from the perspective of soil loss on cropland seem to be the central part of NFH and the western half of AVL.

Figure 10: AT - Change of modelled soil erosion for period 2021-2040 according to RCP4.5, relative to Task 3.1 results.

Figure 11 : AT - Change of modelled soil erosion for period 2041-2060 according to RCP4.5, relative to Task 3.1 results.

Figure 12 : AT - Change of modelled soil erosion for period 2061-2080 according to RCP4.5, relative to Task 3.1 results.

In the RCP 8.5 scenario, some reduction of soil loss rates can be found in the 2021-2040 period, especially in NFH, SFH and parts of WMV (Fig. 13). Other areas show increased soil loss rates.

The other two time periods look very similar scenario for 2021-2040, reductions in soil loss rates can be seen in some areas, such as most of SFH, the central part of WMV and the eastern part of AVL. Others show increasing soil loss rates of around 10-40%, such as the western part of AVL, most of NFH, or the eastern part of SFH.

In the following time periods 2041-2060 and 2061-2080, the changes get somewhat muted and relative differences are generally lower. NFH and WMV turn mostly into slight reductions. The area's most concerning from the perspective of soil loss on cropland seem to be the central part of NFH and the western half of AVL.

Figure 13 : AT - Change of modelled soil erosion for period 2021-2040 according to RCP8.5, relative to Task 3.1 results.

Figure 14 : AT - Change of modelled soil erosion for period 2041-2060 according to RCP8.5, relative to Task 3.1 results.

Figure 15 : AT - Change of modelled soil erosion for period 2061-2080 according to RCP8.5, relative to Task 3.1 results.

These results are summarized and aggregated to MAPZ level in Table 8.

Table 8 : AT – Change of soil loss rates relative to 1991-2020 reference scenario per main agricultural production zone (MAPZ).

Scenario \ MAPZ	HA	VA	AOR	WMV	KB	AVL	SFH	NFH
RCP4.5 relative diff 2021-2040 mean	-0.01	0.12	-0.0	0.05	-0.06	0.12	-0.05	0.09
RCP4.5 relative diff 2041-2060 mean	-0.05	0.04	-0.1	-0.11	-0.12	0.00	-0.12	-0.09
RCP4.5 relative diff 2061-2080 mean	-0.05	0.06	-0.1	-0.05	-0.08	0.04	-0.05	-0.08
RCP8.5 relative diff 2021-2040 mean	-0.02	0.03	-0.0	0.06	0.11	0.09	-0.07	-0.15
RCP8.5 relative diff 2041-2060 mean	0.13	0.23	0.17	0.07	0.19	0.21	0.25	0.11
RCP8.5 relative diff 2061-2080 mean	0.01	0.17	0.03	0.18	0.13	0.22	0.12	0.09

Conclusions

We want to stress that this simplified sensitivity analysis, where only R-factors are changed, is unlikely to be representative of future developments. It seems likely that crop rotations are going to be different from the current situation as a result of the changed environmental conditions. Main and catch be impacted in their development - canopy cover, soil cover and infiltration would likely be impacted by dry spells at the same time, leading to higher soil loss by water. While reduced R-factor from supposedly reduced daily rainfall sums might seem beneficial from an erosion point of view, it may go hand in hand with increased rainfall intensities. These considerations are out of scope of this exercise.

Part 2: Greenhouse gas and climate regulation and carbon sequestration, primary biomass production and the ST soil nutrient imbalance.

We projected grassland production of five regions into the future following the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 pathways. We simulated regional soil specific greenhouse gas emissions, soil nitrous oxide emissions, soil carbon stocks, nitrate leaching and primary biomass production for the three decades 2026-2035, 2046-2055 and 2065-2075. We have also considered the impact of management changes on the same parameters. We particularly looked at the implementation of one of the more popular agri-environmental measures for biodiversity-friendly management and the Green Deal target of 25% organic farming.

Methods

The five representative grassland regions AT Ennstal, AT Grieskirchen, AT Muehviertel, AT Oststeirisches Hueggelland and AT Rheintal (Fig. 16) differ in altitude, precipitation pattern, intensity of grassland production and soil properties. Detailed descriptions can be found in Amon 2018 and Foldal et al. 2019.

Figure 16 : AT - Austrian grassland regions modelled and mapped in SERENA.

Modelling tool

The process-based ecosystem model LandscapeDNDC - version 1.35.2 was applied to run the simulation of future climate change scenarios. The model used in this project is well described in Haas et al. (2013). The model has been validated with Austrian conditions during previous projects (see e.g. Foldal et al., 2019; Kasper et al., 2019; Schroeck et al., 2019). For running the model, LandscapeDNDC

required measured data for geographical parameters and soil parameters in different soil depths, detailed region-specific land use and management practices and daily weather. Furthermore, mean regional yields and fertilization and calculated data of mean regional nitrogen (N) deposition are considered. The required information exists on different scales. Spatial information on land use and soil properties was taken from the Austria digital soil map (eBod 2017). Hectare and yields of grassland categories (2005 – 2014), number of cattle in the regions (2007 – 2014) was held from the Statistics Austria and the INVEKOS database. N deposition, climate and management are generated on regional level, whereas soil parameters used for modelling are site specific. In detail, the following input data is: *Site parameters*: latitude, longitude, annual precipitation, slope, elevation etc.; *Soil data*: humus type, soil type, texture, stone fraction, bulk density, C_{org} , N_{org} , pH, soil moisture, wilting point, WHC, etc. of all soil layers; *N-Deposition*: regional annual wet and dry N deposition from EMEP-modelling, downscaled to 1x1 km; *Climate data*: air temperature (mean, min, max), precipitation, air humidity, wind speed, global radiation; at a daily time resolution; *Management*: regional cut intensities; regional yield; area (ha) of intensive and extensive under non-organic and organic farming systems.

Management scenarios:

Table 9 shows the region-specific grassland management of AT Ennstal, AT Grieskirchen, AT Muehlviertel, AT Oststeirisches Hügelland and AT Rheintal for the baseline period 2005-2014. Non-organic intensive management with three or more cuts is predominant.

- 1) First, we assessed the impact of climate change by projecting the baseline of the prevailing non-organic intensive grassland management into the future.
- 2) Secondly, we added on top of the climate change the effect if 7% of the regional area (all grassland soils) were managed according to the biodiversity-friendly management promoted by the Austrian agri-environmental measures. The 7% comes from the target set by the Austrian government for the current CAP period to be achieved by 2027. Under this management, meadows are mown only twice a season, with the first mowing not taking place before the end of June. Fertilizer is only applied after cutting (AMA 2024). Consequently, under this extensive management, the amount of N fertilizer applied per ha is reduced by approximately 45-70%.
- 3) Finally, we asked what would happen if all regions met the Green Deal target of 25% organic production, additionally to scenario 2. This scenario was only considered for the three representative regions AT Ennstal, AT Grieskirchen and AT Oststeirisches Hügelland, for which we have detailed statistical information. In organic farming the number of livestock and therefore the amount of manure is lower. Mineral fertilizers are not allowed and thereby the main difference between non-organic and organic management is a lower application of N-fertilizer.

Table 9 : AT - Overview of regional ratio of management (area) given in the regions in the period 2005-2014 (Baseline). The share of intensive and extensive management is similar in organic and non-organic farming in the given regions.

Region	intensiv	extensive	organic	non-organic
AT Ennstal	84%	16%	26%	74%
AT Grieskirchen	93%	7%	11%	89%
AT Muehlviertel	97%	3%	NA	
AT Oststeirisches Huegelland	66%	34%	10%	90%
AT Rheintal	80%	205	NA	

Climate scenario description:

We applied the two climate projection scenarios RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 having a forcing value in 2100 of 4.5 W m⁻² and 8.5 W m⁻² respectively (IPCC et al. 2013). In RCP 4.5 the atmospheric CO₂ concentration increased to 537 ppm in 2100 and in RCP8.5 to 926 ppm. Table 10 shows the atmospheric CO₂ concentration given under the baseline in 2010 and for the scenarios in 2030, 2050 and 2070 for both pathways.

Table 10 : AT – Atmospheric CO₂ concentration in ppm from the simulation input files under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. Values from the corresponding years are listed.

scenario	2010	2030	2050	2070
rcp 4.5	389	435	486	524
rcp 8.5		448	540	677

We have used an ensemble of global climate models (GCMs):

- **Earth-EC:** developed by a European consortium of national weather services and research institutes.
- **GFDL-CM3:** the global climate model of the Global Fluid Dynamics Laboratories
- **HadGEM2:** the Hadley Centre Global Environment Model version 2, which includes a coupled atmosphere-ocean configuration with dynamic vegetation, ocean biology and atmospheric chemistry.
- **MIROC5:** (Model for Interdisciplinary Research On Climate), developed by the Japanese research community
- **MPI-ESM:** from the Max Planck Institute Earth System Model

Based on historical regional measured weather data, the stochastic Long Ashton Research Station Weather Generator (LARS-WG) was used to project local daily time series of observed weather (temperature, precipitation and radiation) considering climate change characteristics derived from GCM simulations for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios.

Simulation periods covering the time periods 2021-2040, 2041-2060 and 2061-2080. For each site, 10 individual climate change time series (seeds) were generated to represent the uncertainty of future climate and to avoid weather generator effects to dominate the climate change impact simulation.

Table 11 shows the decadal mean air temperature and annual precipitation rates of the climate stations across all models and generated local weather (n= 50 per RCP) for the measured weather between 2005-2014 (2010), 2026-2035 (2030s), 2046-2055 (2050s) and 2066-2075 (2070s).

Table 11 : AT - Mean annual temperature (°C) and sum of annual precipitation (mm) of baseline and the relative change in the climate scenarios (across all models and seeds) following the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 pathway.

scenario	region	climate station	mean temperature (°C)				mean precipitation(mm)			
			2010	2030	2050	2070	2010	2030	2050	2070
rcp 4.5	AT_ET	Aigen	8.3	9.3	9.7	10.6	967	1003	996	1011
		Irdning	8.5	10.0	10.2	11.0	1230	1072	1029	1050
	AT_GK	Kremsuenster	10.3	11.3	11.7	12.3	1026	1032	1010	1022
	AT_MV	Rohrbach	8.7	9.8	10.1	10.7	933	978	978	988
	AT_OH	Hartberg	10.7	11.7	12.1	12.6	783	759	747	765
	AT_RT	Bregenz	10.7	11.4	12.1	12.4	1640	1620	1621	1643
		Feldkirch	10.5	11.3	11.8	12.5	1222	1273	1245	1269
rcp 8.5	AT_ET	Aigen	8.3	9.4	10.2	11.7	967	1029	1018	972
		Irdning	8.5	9.8	10.6	12.3	1230	1086	1022	965
	AT_GK	Kremsuenster	10.3	11.4	12.1	13.4	1026	1031	1033	996
	AT_MV	Rohrbach	8.7	9.9	10.5	12	933	991	977	968
	AT_OH	Hartberg	10.7	11.7	12.6	13.8	783	779	762	725
	AT_RT	Bregenz	10.7	11.7	12.5	14.1	1640	1641	1636	1567
		Feldkirch	10.5	11.4	12.2	13.7	1222	1280	1265	1241

We see an overall increase in mean annual temperature from the near to the far future, with a greater effect under RCP 8.5. Apart from AT ET Irdning, there are only minor changes in annual precipitation. During the baseline period the weather stations AT Irdning and AT Aigen differ significantly in temperature and precipitation. Therefore, we simulated both stations in the same valley even though they are geographically close. It seems that we lost this precision when downscaling the GLMs, which led to a larger change in precipitation at AT Irdning compared to AT Aigen.

For all data management, describing statistic and boxplots we used R studio version 4.3.1. The maps were drawn in QGIS 3.1.

Results

Impact of Climate Change on the SES S GHG and climate regulation (N₂O emissions) and C sequestration (soil organic carbon stock), ST Soil nutrient imbalance (NO₃⁻ leaching) and SES Biomass production (yield) under business-as-usual in non-organic farming grassland production.

In general, the emissions of N₂O and NO₃⁻ leaching decreases in both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios (range from -10 to -89%), only in AT Ennstal future N₂O emissions are projected to increase by 5 to 45% (Table 12). Regarding C sequestration and biomass production, a slight increase in soil carbon stocks (top 30 cm) by 0.9 to 5.6% and an increase in mean yields of 5 to 44% are simulated. The mean yields are always greater in RCP 8.5.

Table 12: AT – Regional mean annual baseline results in kg ha⁻¹ of soil nitrous oxide emissions (N₂O - N), soil organic carbon stock (SOC), nitrate leaching (NO₃⁻-N) and biomass production as yield DW and subsequently the relative difference by simulating climate change under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 pathway for three decades compared to baseline of all five regions. A number is printed in bold when the N loss is reduced by > 50%.

Scenario	time period	unit	mean N ₂ O-N	mean SOC	mean NO ₃ ⁻ -N	mean yield DW
AT Ennstal						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha ⁻¹]	0.67	71574	3.21	6366
	2026-2035		32.7	2.2	-9.7	26.8
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	17.2	2.5	-23.6	32.0
	2066-2075		21.3	2.7	-18.8	34.6
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		21.7	2.2	-24.7	33.3
	2046-2055	% change	5.3	2.9	-43.9	40.7
	2066-2075		43.7	3.9	31.2	38.8
AT Grieskirchen						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha ⁻¹]	0.84	73076	0.39	8395
	2026-2035		-12.4	4.0	-40.6	15.1
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-16.2	4.5	-46.9	19.3
	2066-2075		-13.6	4.6	-53.4	20.3
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		-18.3	4.0	-48.5	18.0
	2046-2055	% change	-19.0	4.7	-59.9	25.2
	2066-2075		-12.2	5.6	-62.5	24.0
AT Muehlviertel						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha ⁻¹]	0.75	93321	2.11	9131
	2026-2035		-22.1	0.9	-46.4	18.7
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-20.9	1.2	-44.9	22.4
	2066-2075		-21.5	1.4	-49.2	25.3
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		-23.6	0.9	-50.2	21.4
	2046-2055	% change	-23.6	1.5	-48.9	26.6
	2066-2075		-22.2	2.2	-54.2	31.0

AT Oststeirisches Hügelland						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	1.29	72274	5.05	7694
	2026-2035		-10.6	2.5	-41.3	5.5
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-21.4	2.9	-49.2	7.6
	2066-2075		-16.3	2.9	-56.5	4.5
	2026-2035		-20.9	2.2	-37.4	9.2
RCP 8.5	2046-2055	% change	-23.4	3.1	-50.9	11.2
	2066-2075		-12.7	4.3	-72.7	-5.6

AT Rheintal						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.71	74864	0.37	9001
	2026-2035		-20.6	2.3	-81.8	26.6
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-20.5	2.5	-84.5	31.8
	2066-2075		-18.8	2.6	-87.4	34.7
	2026-2035		-21.0	2.4	-80.8	28.4
RCP 8.5	2046-2055	% change	-22.7	2.8	-89.1	36.8
	2066-2075		-16.8	3.1	-87.2	43.9

Due to the geoclimatic conditions, the Austrian grassland production area is a mosaic of mainly small-scale heterogeneous fields. In Fig. 17 - 21 we show the regional soil specific spatial distribution of N₂O emissions, soil carbon stocks, NO₃⁻ leaching and yield production in Austrian mountainous grassland. Furthermore, the simulated trends are summarized as boxplots. The box plots describe the large variability in soil and climate over time. We address the regional results directly after the figures below.

Figure 17 : AT - A, B, C and D show the mean annual spatial distribution of soil N₂O emissions, soil organic carbon stock, NO₃ leaching and yield for the baseline in AT Ennstal respectively, whereas a, b, c and d show the trend of changes following the RCP 4.5 (green) and 8.5 (blue) climate change scenarios over three time periods for the same parameters. a, b, c and d, include all soil types and all simulation runs.

As can be seen from the box plots in Fig. 17 a) N₂O emissions in AT Ennstal will increase and are expected to be higher under RCP4.5 than under RCP 8.5. Especially in the far future, the variability and the years with peak emissions will increase. In the future the soil organic carbon stocks will increase (AT17b) whereas the amount of N lost by leaching will decrease (AT17c). The biomass production is projected to increase, however with larger uncertainty for the producers, years of extremely high yields can be followed by years, where only half of normal yield is harvested. The uncertainty increases under more intense climate change.

Figure 18 : AT - A, B, C and D show the mean annual spatial distribution of soil N₂O emissions, soil organic carbon stock, NO₃- leaching and yield for the baseline in AT Grieskirchen respectively, whereas a, b, c and d show the trend of changes following the RCP 4.5 (green) and 8.5 (blue) climate change scenarios over three time periods for the same parameters. a, b, c and d, include all soil types and all simulation runs.

In AT Grieskirchen, the future projections show that the N_2O emissions are expected to decrease (At18a), the content of SOC slightly increases (At18b), whereas the amount of N lost by leaching will decrease (AT18c) and yields will increase. Overall, the variability and the years with “peak emissions” increase, especially in the far future.

Figure 19 : AT - A, B, C and D show the mean annual spatial distribution of soil N_2O emissions, soil organic carbon stock, NO_3 - leaching and yield for the baseline in AT Muehlviertel respectively, whereas a, b, c and d show the trend of changes following the RCP 4.5 (green) and 8.5 (blue) climate change scenarios over three time periods for the same parameters. a, b, c and d, include all soil types and all simulation runs.

In AT Muehlviertel N_2O emissions and loss of nutrients by NO_3 - (AT19 a and c) are projected to be similar reduced in both RCP4.5 and RCP 8.5. The SOC stock (AT19b) will remain high and increase slightly, especially in the last period of this assessment. Mean yields are increasing (AT19d), whereby the uncertainty, like in the other regions, increase by climate change intensity.

Figure 20 : AT - A, B, C and D show the mean annual spatial distribution of soil N₂O emissions, soil organic carbon stock, NO₃⁻ leaching and yield for the baseline in AT Oststeirisches Huegelland respectively, whereas a, b, c and d show the trend of changes following the RCP 4.5 (green) and 8.5 (blue) climate change scenarios over three time periods for the same parameters. a, b, c and d, include all soil types and all simulation runs.

In AT Oststeirisches Huegelland, the N_2O emissions are expected to decrease (At20a) in the future projections. Furthermore, the content of SOC will slightly increase (At20b), whereas amount of N lost by leaching will decrease (AT20c). In the near and middle future there will be an overall increase in yield production. Whereby in the far future, the years of less yield are dominating so that at average the yield production will be reduced. Overall, the variability and the years with peak emissions increase.

Figure 21 : AT - A, B, C and D show the mean annual spatial distribution of soil N_2O emissions, soil organic carbon stock, NO_3 - leaching and yield for the baseline in AT Rheintal respectively, whereas a, b, c and d show the trend of changes following the RCP 4.5 (green) and 8.5 (blue) climate change scenarios over three time periods for the same parameters. a, b, c and d, include all soil types and all simulation runs.

In AT Rheintal N_2O emissions and loss of nutrients by NO_3^- (AT21 a and c) are projected to be similar reduced in both RCP4.5 and RCP 8.5. The soil organic carbon stock (AT21b) will remain high and increase slightly, especially in the last period of this assessment. Mean yields are increasing (AT21d), whereby the uncertainty, like in the other regions, increase by climate change intensity.

Impact of Climate Change and increase of biodiversity-friendly management

The effect of climate change and the implementation of biodiversity-friendly grassland production (less and late use) on 7% of the area gives similar results (Tab. 13) for mean NO_3^- leaching, SOC stock and mean production as described above in Tab. 12. The simulated N_2O emissions are also similar, with an increase in AT Ennstal and decrease in the other regions.

Table 13 : AT – Regional mean annual baseline results in $kg\ ha^{-1}$ of soil nitrous oxide emissions (N_2O - N), nitrate leaching (NO_3^- -N), soil organic carbon stock (SOC) and biomass production as yield DW and subsequently the relative difference by simulating climate change under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5

pathway and implementation of biodiversity-friendly management over 7% of area for three decades compared to baseline of all five regions. Numbers are in bold when mean annual N loss is reduced by >50%.

Scenario	time period	unit	mean N ₂ O-N	mean SOC	mean NO ₃ -N	mean yield DW
AT Ennstal						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.64	71528	3.03	6236
	2026-2035		36.2	2.3	-3.4	28.5
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	17.7	2.7	-23.6	33.8
	2066-2075		21.5	2.8	-20.0	36.1
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		21.4	2.2	-24.8	32.5
	2046-2055	% change	5.6	2.9	-43.0	39.9
	2066-2075		44.3	4.0	36.4	37.8
AT Grieskirchen						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.82	73023	0.38	8257
	2026-2035		-12.8	4.1	-41.5	13.8
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-16.4	4.6	-47.4	18.0
	2066-2075		-13.5	4.7	-53.6	18.9
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		-18.5	4.1	-49.2	16.7
	2046-2055	% change	-18.9	4.8	-60.1	23.8
	2066-2075		-11.9	5.7	-62.5	22.4
AT Muehlviertel						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.71	93293	2.03	8961
	2026-2035		-21.4	0.9	-45.7	18.6
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-20.0	1.2	-44.0	22.3
	2066-2075		-20.4	1.5	-48.3	25.1
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		-23.6	0.9	-50.2	21.4
	2046-2055	% change	-23.6	1.5	-48.9	26.6
	2066-2075		-22.2	2.2	-54.2	31.0
AT Oststeirisches Huegelland						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	1.23	72142	5.04	7496
	2026-2035		-10.0	2.5	-41.4	5.2
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-20.4	3.0	-49.3	7.2
	2066-2075		-15.4	3.0	-56.6	4.2
RCP 8.5	2026-2035		-20.1	2.3	-37.4	9.0
	2046-2055	% change	-22.4	3.2	-50.9	10.8
	2066-2075		-12.2	4.4	-72.8	-5.8
AT Rheintal						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.67	74861	0.35	8765
	2026-2035		-19.8	2.4	-81.9	26.6
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-19.4	2.6	-84.5	31.8
	2066-2075		-17.6	2.8	-87.2	34.7

	2026-2035		-20.2	2.4	-80.9	28.4
RCP 8.5	2046-2055	% change	-21.5	2.9	-89.0	36.9
	2066-2075		-15.4	3.3	-86.9	43.9

Impact of Climate Change, increase of biodiversity-friendly management and organic farming

Under both climate change pathways, an implementation of biodiversity-friendly management and organic farming on 25% of the agricultural area have a similar effect on N₂O emissions, SOC stocks, NO₃ leaching and yield production as previously described scenarios. Here it is likely that climate change will mostly affect the loss of nitrogen (ST nutrient imbalance) and reduce this ST by 9-72%. N₂O emissions will still increase in AT Ennstal, however in all regions the mean SOC stock mostly increases in the time periods by 2-5.5% and mean annual yields increases by 4-40% (Table 14).

Table 14 : AT – Regional mean annual baseline results in kg ha⁻¹ of soil nitrous oxide emissions (N₂O - N), soil organic carbon stock (SOC), nitrate leaching (NO₃⁻-N) and biomass production as yield DW and subsequently the relative difference by simulating climate change under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 pathway, implementation of biodiversity-friendly management over 7% of area and organic farming system over 25% of the area for three decades compared to baseline in three representative regions.

Scenario	time period	unit	mean N ₂ O-N	mean SOC	mean NO ₃ -N	mean yield DW
AT Ennstal						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.53	71121	2.53	5952
	2026-2035		27.9	2.1	-9.3	27.9
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	14.1	2.4	-25.2	33.2
	2066-2075		17.3	2.6	-21.1	35.8
	2026-2035		-1.0	2.0	-29.4	31.8
RCP 8.5	2046-2055	% change	-15.5	2.7	-44.2	39.5
	2066-2075		22.6	3.6	46.1	38.4
AT Grieskirchen						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	0.68	72476	0.31	7941
	2026-2035		-12.0	3.9	-42.6	13.8
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-15.0	4.3	-48.3	18.2
	2066-2075		-12.2	4.5	-54.3	19.4
	2026-2035		-17.3	3.9	-50.2	16.8
RCP 8.5	2046-2055	% change	-17.2	4.6	-60.6	24.2
	2066-2075		-10.2	5.5	-62.7	23.8
AT Oststeirisches Huegelland						
Baseline	2005-2014	[kg ha⁻¹]	1.05	71564	5.07	7266
	2026-2035		-8.1	2.4	-41.0	4.9
RCP 4.5	2046-2055	% change	-17.3	2.9	-48.6	7.1
	2066-2075		-12.1	3.0	-56.1	4.4
RCP 8.5	2026-2035	% change	-17.3	2.2	-37.0	8.7

2046-2055	-8.9	4.1	-51.2	14.4
2066-2075	-9.7	4.2	-72.3	-4.9

Effect of management change without considering climate change.

The implementation of agri-environmental measures such as biodiversity-friendly grassland management and organic farming reduces the mean annual N₂O emissions by 3-21%, soil C sequestration potential or SOC stock by 0-1%, loss of excess N as NO₃- by 0-21% and mean annual yields by 2-7%. The simulations were run over the baseline period with the current daily climate, across all soils and sites in the regions.

Interestingly, the reductions are lower in the regions with the highest production potential (AT Grieskirchen, AT Muehlviertel, AT Rheintal). Furthermore, the relative reduction of N losses as GHG or by leaching are both greater than the relative loss of yield. Regarding the mean SOC stock this is greater under intensive grassland production and any implementation of the management scenarios is likely to reduce the SOC stock over time (Table 15).

Table 15 : AT – Comparing the effect of non-organic intensive grassland management with non-organic intensive + biodiversity friendly management and non-organic intensive + biodiversity friendly management + organic farming across the five regions on soil nitrous oxide emissions (N₂O -N), soil organic carbon stock (SOC), nitrate leaching (NO₃--N) and biomass production (yield DW).

management	mean N ₂ O-N	mean SOC	mean NO ₃ -N	mean yield DW
AT Ennstal				
Non-organic intensive	0.67	71574	3.21	6366
+biodiversity friendly	-4.46	-0.09	-7.77	-2.91
+ biodiversity friendly + organic	-21.15	-0.63	-21.01	-6.51
AT Grieskirchen				
Non-organic intensive	0.84	73076	0.39	8395
+biodiversity friendly	-3.2	-0.1	-3.1	-1.6
+ biodiversity friendly + organic	-18.9	-0.8	-21.2	-5.4
AT Muehlviertel				
Non-organic intensive	0.75	93321	2.11	9131
+biodiversity friendly	-4.9	0.0	-3.9	-1.9
AT Oststeirisches Huegelland				
Non-organic intensive	1.29	72274	5.05	7694
+biodiversity friendly	-4.3	-0.2	0.0	-2.6
+ biodiversity friendly + organic	-18.5	-1.0	0.5	-5.6
AT Rheintal				
Non-organic intensive	0.71	74864	0.37	9001
+biodiversity friendly	-5.3	0.0	-6.0	-2.6

Discussion - GHG regulation, C sequestration, Biomass productivity, N-leaching

Interestingly, we see that future implementation of biodiversity-friendly measures at 7% of the agricultural area not only enhances biodiversity but additionally reduces the loss of leached N in form of nitrate by 9-63%. The effect is regional specific and greater at higher climate change intensities. In some regions, this single measure would already be sufficient to meet the Green Deal targets.

N₂O emissions are projected to decrease. Soil carbon stocks are projected to increase, and nutrient losses (NO₃) and crop production will decrease. However, the increase in the number of “peak years” and, in particular, the decrease in the predictability of yield production will be important stressors, which will probably be decisive for the continuation or abandonment of agricultural production.

In this study, we have projected region-specific management into future climate scenarios. A limitation of the study is the lack of adaptation of management steps to the given future climate. We see that “peak years” of all parameters are increasing in the future, and farmers could and would apply their management depending on the past, actual and predicted weather. However, a dynamic management input-file was beyond the scope of this study as it would add further complexity to the already advanced assessment.

Conclusions and recommendations

High-resolution soil data, especially in a small-scale agriculture such as in Austria, models capable of simulating sets of indicators to assess SES and ST are important to obtain realistic predictions of future changes.

More field measurements are needed in the future to develop, improve and validate such models. This is particularly true for those SES and ST for which models are not yet available (e.g. biodiversity loss).

Data availability: Even if we already can access and model with more or less detailed field data compiled in the Austrian Digital Soil Map (eBod, <https://www.bodenkarte.at/>), some of these datasets are old and we strongly recommend updating the database regularly by implementing a harmonized monitoring program such as e.g. proposed in the Soil Monitoring Act.

Part 3: Land use change

BOX 3.4.1: Land Use Change in Vorarlberg

Past, recent and future soil threats have an impact on SES. We applied the SERENA Cookbook approach in T3.2 to address past land use change for the year 2018. Furthermore, we analyzed the outcome of LUISA-prognosis for the year 2050, parallel to T5.2.

Vorarlberg is a mountainous region with few, but highly productive soils and the land is expected to become a more important agricultural region in future scenarios. Vorarlberg has had a steadily growing population for decades, and is close to an attractive labour market, including in neighbouring countries.

In 2018, 67 000 ha of land in Vorarlberg were covered by building land and traffic and transport areas. The total land consumption (including areas for recreation etc.) was 40.5% of the permanent settlement area. Only 22.5% of Vorarlberg is defined as permanent settlement area, which includes all land except steep mountains, rivers and water bodies, and (Umweltbundesamt, 2022).

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4.2 Scenario analyses – Czech Republic

Introduction

In the Czech Republic, soil compaction quantification under different land use and climate change scenarios offers insights into future environmental and agricultural challenges. SSP1-2.6 called “sustainability” pathway projects a world based on green growth with sustainable land use and low carbon emissions. In contrast SSP5-8.5 “Fossil-fueled-development” pathway, projects a world driven by rapid economic growth with high dependence on fossil fuels and intensive land use. In this scenario, intense land use change are the drivers that may influence the change in bulk density. This report presents the quantification and mapping of compaction in Czech Republic and their evolution under SSP1-2.6, SSP5-8.5 and land use scenarios by 2050.

- **Soil threat:** Compaction

Indicator: change over time in topsoil bulk density

- **Land use:** Land Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment (LUISA)
- **Climate change scenarios:** SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5. We selected these two contrasting scenarios in order to explore different futures for national development of the Czech Republic and their implications for climate and land use change over bulk density.
- **Connection to other Deliverables or WPs in Serena:** The methods used in WP5, as clearly detailed in Deliverable D5.1 (Coblisnki et al., 2023), were applied. The indicator selected was bulk density, and the soil threat was defined as "change over time in topsoil bulk density" as stated in Deliverable D5.1.

Methods

We applied the same methods than WP5 (Coblisnki et al., 2023) summarised as follows:

- We employed digital soil mapping to project the bulk density, based on Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) algorithm. The algorithm was fitted with the covariates for the present, and the model was used to predict under land use and climate change scenarios by 2050.
- The assessment of the model performance was done by repeated cross validation.
- Soil compaction was calculated as the difference in bulk density in topsoil (0-30 cm) between 2022 and 2050.

Results

Change in bulk density for Czech Republic (100 m resolution)

- a. The most important variable used for predicting bulk density in 2022 was clay content (Fig. 24). Other important variables are elevation, land use and climate. Soil organic carbon content does not appear to have significant influence in bulk density. The prediction of bulk density for 2022 indicates that the change will be associated to clay, elevation, climate and land use (Fig. 24).

Figure 24 : CZ - Variable importance.

- b. The cross validation show that the model had an excellent performance with R^2 of 0.88 and RMSE of 0.04 (Table 16).

Table 16 : CZ – Model performance.

metric	R2	RMSE	MAE	CCC
value	0.88	0.04	0.03	0.93

- c. By 2050, the mean bulk density of Czech soils is not expected to have changed substantially from 2023, regardless of the scenarios analysed (Table 17). According to the SSP1-2.6 and SSP5-8.5 scenarios, 0.08% and 0.45% of Czech soils are projected to experience a substantial increase in bulk density, while 28% and 30% are anticipated to undergo a moderate change, respectively (Fig. 25). The mentioned increases will primarily occur in the northeast and northwest, with the highest intensity of compaction in the southwest. While the difference between the two scenarios regarding bulk density changes from 2022 to 2050 is not substantial when considering the entire country, some regions exhibit a more pronounced increase in bulk density under the SSP1-2.6 scenario compared to the SSP5-8.5 scenario (Fig. 25).

Table 17 : CZ – Descriptive statistics of the change (%) between 1970 and 2050 in bulk density under land use and climate change scenarios.

Compaction	Unit	Scenario	Mean	SD	CV
	%	1-2.6	3.52	7.94	2.14
		5-8.5	3.98	7.87	1.97

Figure 25 : CZ - Change in bulk density. a) SSP1-2.6 and b) SSP5-8.5 scenarios.

Conclusions and recommendations:

The change in the bulk density between the present and the future in both scenarios of climate change and land use, reveal an increasing risk of compaction in vulnerable regions. These changes could significantly impact soil health, crop productivity, and ecosystem resilience.

To reduce the risk of soil compaction in the short term, sustainable land management and conservation practices are of great importance. In the medium-term monitoring will provide the data to spot areas of high risk that need intervention. In the long-term promoting regulations and policy that limit heavy machinery usage and adaptive management practices to mitigate future risk of compaction associated with land use and climate change.

Acknowledgements: We thank to Daniel Žižala from the Research Institute for Soil and Water Conservation, Prague Czech Republic for providing the national data.

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4.3 Scenario analyses – Estonia

Part 1: GHG regulation

Introduction

This study utilized the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios to assess the soil ecosystem service of GHG and climate regulation under different levels of climate change. RCP4.5 represents a moderate mitigation scenario with significant global emission reduction efforts, while RCP8.5 is a high-emission scenario reflecting continued reliance on fossil fuels and weak international cooperation. These scenarios help evaluate the impact of varying GHG concentration pathways on soil ecosystems.

The scenarios were developed using the GHG Cookbook's NEP (Net Ecosystem Productivity) calculations from the SERENA project, which incorporates MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) terrestrial primary production products, along with climatic variables in spatially explicit databases, such as average temperatures derived from minimum and maximum temperatures and soil volumetric moisture. The NEP was assessed based on projections of average temperature and soil moisture for the RCP scenarios, assuming that the MODIS inputs remain stable.

Methods

a) Net ecosystem productivity (NEP):

The study was carried out using Peipsiääre municipality in Estonia as a case study, utilizing the NEP (Net Ecosystem Productivity) layer provided by the SERENA GHG Cookbook application as the reference. This reference layer facilitated an 8-day NEP analysis in winter wheat fields within Peipsiääre, based on soil moisture data from April 24 to May 1, 2014, and the average temperature for April 2014.

For the climate change scenarios, the same methodology was applied using projected average temperatures and soil moisture data under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, with projections drawn by Luhamaa et al. (2014) and the Climate Information Data Access Platform. Both sources utilized regional downscaling of global climate projections from CMIP5 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5). In the graphical representation of NEP projections for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, cubic spline interpolation was applied to fit continuous curves through the data points, resulting in a visually smooth representation of the data. NEP scenarios for the periods 2041-2070 and 2070-2100 under these RCP pathways were subsequently assessed.

Results

a) Net ecosystem productivity (NEP):

In the reference layer, NEP values in Peipsiääre municipality ranged from -8 to 25.3 gC m⁻², with a weighted average of 8.68 gC m⁻² over an 8-day period (D3.3 - Assessment of Soil Threats and Ecosystem Services from each MS with Harmonized Procedures). Under the RCP4.5 pathway, NEP shows a decline during the periods 2041-2070 and 2071-2100, with a more pronounced decrease observed in the latter period (Fig. 26).

Figure 26 : EE - The 8-day NEP in wheat fields in Peipsiääre municipality under the RCP4.5 pathway for the periods 2041-2070 and 2071-2100.

Compared to RCP4.5, RCP8.5 leads to a more significant reduction in NEP values, while the losses under RCP4.5 are more moderate (Fig. 27). In 2014, the majority of the area falls within the 5-10 and 10-15 gC m⁻² NEP ranges, encompassing more than three-quarters of the wheat-growing region. However, by 2071-2100, much of this area is projected to shift to lower NEP ranges, particularly within the 0-5 gC m⁻² range and below, indicating a potential transition towards diminished carbon uptake or even carbon release during the 8-day NEP period at the end of April.

Figure 27: EE - Modeled NEP values over an 8-day period under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, compared with the reference year 2014.

Conclusions and recommendations

The combination of increased temperatures and decreased soil moisture under both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios led to a decline in NEP in Peipsiääre municipality. This decrease is mainly attributable to an expected increase in ecosystem respiration due to higher temperatures during the analyzed period.

The response of NEP to these changes may vary based on specific local conditions, such as vegetation type, soil properties, and the magnitude of temperature and moisture variations. Therefore, for more accurate future assessments, it is essential to incorporate detailed site-specific factors into climate change scenario analysis. Additionally, as the current analysis of NEP scenarios was based on an 8-day period at the end of April, expanding the study to cover a longer timeframe and larger spatial area would offer a more comprehensive understanding of seasonal variations, along with a detailed assessment of regional dynamics. Variability in terrestrial primary productivity under future climate scenarios can influence the rate and direction of ecosystem carbon fluxes, subsequently altering net ecosystem production. Integration of these dynamics to climate change models would enhance the accuracy of projections. While refining the approach and validating data to address Estonia's pedoclimatic conditions is necessary, this study offers valuable initial insights into NEP modeling under climate change scenarios.

Part 2: SOC loss

Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) has a significant role in maintaining soil health and fertility, influencing agricultural productivity and environmental sustainability. However, various land use practices can significantly affect SOC stocks, leading to potential losses that impact the provision of soil ecosystem services (SES). With the expectation that agricultural fields in North European regions will increasingly have year-round vegetation in the future, this study analyzes two contrasting land management scenarios: bare soil during the winter months and continuous vegetation.

This analysis is connected to the previous deliverables of the SERENA project by broadening the examination of SOC loss to include an assessment of land management scenarios. The main objective of this study is to evaluate the effects of winter cropping systems on long-term soil fertility and their potential to mitigate SOC loss compared to bare soil conditions during the winter months. By focusing on Elva Parish as a case study, this research aims to offer insights into the implications of different land management practices on SOC stocks over the period from 2020 to 2040.

Methods

This analysis evaluated changes in SOC stocks (0-30 cm) at the field level in Elva Parish over the period 2020–2040, using different land-use scenarios. The modeling used a SOC stock map layer for Estonian mineral arable land soils developed by the Centre of Estonian Rural Research and Knowledge, with a resolution of 40 x 40 m per pixel. This map integrates SOC concentrations determined from soil samples collected between 2015–2020 from arable fields (PANDA database) and represents the 2020 baseline conditions. Each 40 x 40 m pixel is defined by its specific SOC stock and clay content class, enabling projections of SOC stocks for individual pixels and facilitating the calculation of the average SOC stock and predicted changes across the study area under different scenarios.

SOC stock projections were made using the RothC model, which simulates soil carbon turnover. The climatic data of period 2000–2020 were used for this analysis. The average carbon inputs from plants and manure were 2.88 t/ha/year and 0.08 t/ha/year, respectively. These average C inputs were calculated based on crop yield data and the amount of manure produced by livestock in Elva Parish during the period 2015–2020.

In the first scenario (scenario 1), the average SOC stock in Elva Parish by 2040 was estimated based on the assumption that the land surface would remain bare, without vegetation, throughout the winter period from October to April. In the second scenario (scenario 2), accounting for the increasing share of winter crops and the expectation that agricultural fields will be covered with vegetation year-round in the future, the SOC stock in Elva Parish was projected under conditions assuming the presence of winter vegetation.

Results

Based on the SOC stock map, in 2020, the weighted average SOC stock of arable fields in Elva Parish was 75.9 t/ha. Some areas within the parish have SOC stocks as high as 200 t/ha (Fig. 28).

Figure 28 : EE - The soil organic carbon (SOC) stock map of Elva Parish for 2020.

Modeling the first scenario (soil cover only in summer during the period 2020–2040) the SOC dynamics projected up to the year 2040, assuming that the annual carbon input remains unchanged compared to the 2015–2020 period, shows a decrease in the weighted average SOC stock of arable soils to 69.0 t ha⁻¹, with certain areas still retaining SOC levels as high as 164 t h⁻¹ y⁻¹ (Fig. 29).

Figure 29 : EE - The soil organic carbon (SOC) stock map of Elva Parish for 2040 (scenario 1 - soil cover only in summer).

The SOC stock changes varied from -2.10 to 0.5 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ (Fig. 30). The SOC losses were greater in areas where the initial SOC stock was higher in 2020.

Figure 30 : EE - Soil organic carbon (SOC) stock changes of Elva Parish during 2020–2040 (scenario 1 - soil cover only in summer).

In scenario 2, where the soil is covered with vegetation year-round, the variation in SOC change is greater (from -2.2 to 0.75 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹) compared to scenario 1 (Fig. 31). Still, the average annual SOC stock decrease is smaller, at -0.12 t ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ and the weighted average SOC stock of arable soils is 73.3 t ha⁻¹ (Fig. 32).

Figure 31 : EE - The soil organic carbon (SOC) stock changes of Elva Parish during 2020–2040 (scenario 2 - the soil is covered with vegetation year-round).

Figure 32 : Soil organic carbon (SOC) stock map of Elva Parish for 2040 (scenario 2 - the soil is covered with vegetation year-round).

Conclusions and recommendations

This study highlights the significant impact of land management practices on SOC stocks in Elva Parish, demonstrating that the implementation of year-round vegetation can mitigate SOC loss compared to bare soil conditions during the winter months. The findings indicate that while SOC stocks are projected to decline under current practices, adopting winter cropping systems has the potential to sustain higher SOC levels, thereby enhancing soil health and contributing to agricultural sustainability.

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4.4 Scenario analyses – France

Introduction

We chose to assess changes in the ecosystem services provided by the soil between 1982 and 2050 in two contrasting areas: Naizin (1,200 ha) in Brittany in western France and the Saclay plateau (2,600ha) in Essonne, south of Paris. These two areas differ in terms of their environmental characteristics (soil, climate), their past and present agricultural production systems (livestock systems in Naizin, cereal systems in Saclay), and also in terms of their territorial dynamics, since Naizin remains an almost exclusively agricultural area, whereas Saclay has undergone a recent urbanisation process that will continue over the coming decades.

The approach used to construct and evaluate scenarios for these areas was identical on both sites and focused on studying changes in 12 indicators of 4 categories of ecosystem services delivered by soil (SES) and 1 soil threats (ST) between 1990 and 2050. Table 18 gives a synthetic view of the SES and ST assessed on the two sites according to different climatic, management and change of use scenarios. The assessed SES categories were Biomass/primary production, Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration, Hydrological control and Environmental pollution control, and the ST was Soil sealing.

Table 18 : Fr - Synoptic table of ecosystem services (ES) and soil threats (ST) assessed for two French sites (Naizin, Saclay) and according to different climate, agricultural management and land use scenarios.

Study area	Ecosystem services considered	Climate scenarios	Land use scenarios	Management scenarios
Naizin (Brittany)	4 ES categories assessed by 12 indicators	RCP 4.5 and RCP8.5 with 3 climatic models (1990-2050)	BAU	-BAU -25% less N input -Organic farming -Energy crop development
Saclay (Paris region)	4 ES categories assessed by 8 indicators + 1 ST (soil sealing)	RCP 4.5 and RCP8.5 with 3 climatic models (1982-2050)	- No change in land use from 1982 to 2050 - Observed and projected urbanisation	BAU

Methods

The study areas

Two study areas have been considered and are referred by the names *Naizin* and *Saclay* of the main municipality covering each study area (Fig. 33).

Figure 33 : FR - Main characteristics of the two study areas (Naizin and Saclay) considered in France.

Naizin

The first study site is a well-documented catchment, draining a surface area of 12 km², located in Brittany region (48°00'N, 2°50'W) in western France (Fig. 33). This catchment belongs to the Environmental Research Observatory AgrHyS (<https://agrhy.s.rennes.hub.inrae.fr/>) as a part of OZCAR Critical Zone Observatory network and eLTER Research Infrastructure.

The climate is temperate with oceanic influence. It is characterized by mean minimum and maximum daily temperatures of 7.6 ± 5.1 °C and 15.7 ± 6.3 °C, respectively, and mean annual rainfall of 844 ± 175 mm. The topography of the catchment is rather gentle, with a few slopes reaching a gradient of 5 %. Elevation ranges from 98 to 140m above sea level. Soils are predominantly Cambisols and Luvisols with a silty loam texture (Walter & Curmi, 1998). Parent material consists of Proterozoic schist covered by a layer of weathered material up to 30m thick and fluvial deposits in bottomland. Soils on the hill slopes are well drained and consist of Dystric Cambisols and Luvisols. They differ downslope in the wetland domain where they are hydromorphic and consist of Epistagnic Fluvisols, Epistagnic Luvisols and Epistagnic Albeluvisols. In the topsoil surface horizon, the clay and silt contents vary from 15% to 28% and from 58 to 72% respectively and the soil organic carbon content varies from 14 g/kg to 6.4 g/kg. The pH ranges from 3.9 to 7.7. It is an intensive mixed agricultural catchment for livestock (pig, dairy and poultry farming) and industrial vegetables production with well-documented land-use history and agricultural practices. Main crops are maize (30 %), grasslands (25 %), winter wheat (20 %) and vegetables (10 %), with a high diversity of cropping systems. Crop rotations range from permanent grasslands to maize monoculture and intensive vegetable production. The main crop rotations or land

uses are: i) permanent silage maize, ii) silage maize – winter cereals, iii) silage maize – winter cereals – vegetables, iv) grain maize – winter cereals – vegetables, v) silage maize – grasslands, vi) grain maize – grasslands, vii) permanent grasslands, viii) woodland and orchards. Cropping systems also differ in terms of fertilisation (mineral, organic, amount, frequency), organic matter input (nature, composition) and crop residues management. Soil ecosystem services modelling was carried out at 530 positions of the Naizin catchment, sampled on a regular triangular grid with 150 m sides, only in agricultural land, permanent meadow and wet grassland located in the bottom valley.

Saclay

The Saclay plateau, is the second study site (Fig. 33). It is a peri-urban agricultural landscape in the Ile-de-France region, south-west of Paris, covering an area of 104 km² with an agricultural area of 26 km². This landscape is composed of a vast, nearly level, plateau ranging from 150 to 160m above sea level, encircled at its northern and southern boundaries respectively by the Bièvre and the Yvette rivers (60m above sea level). Its geological stratification is typical of the Parisian Basin (Jamagne, 2011) with loess deposits several meters deep overlaying a claybed rich in millstone, a sand deposit of several tens of meters thick, and, finally, marl deposits (Megnien, 1989). On top plateau positions, Luvisol developed in the thick loess deposits (Scammacca et al., 2023). With the progressively decreasing thickness of the loess deposit and the exposure of underlying clayey materials from the top to the edge of plateau positions, Luvisol of increasing hydromorphy finally shifted to Planosol (Scammacca et al., 2023). Regosol and Arenosol developed in the upslope coarse colluvic materials while Cambisol of increasing hydromorphy were observed in the downslope fine colluvic materials (Scammacca et al., 2023). Finally, Stagnosols characterized valley areas (Scammacca et al., 2023).

Initially a marshy area due to the presence of the shallow claybed, the plateau evolved into a fertile area after its artificial drainage through a complex network of swales at the end of the 17th century (Tedesco et al., 2017). Starting in the valley and progressively affecting the slopes and finally the top plateau positions, urban development progressively transformed this agricultural area to a more and more urbanized area, particularly after the initiation in the second half of the twentieth century of an ambitious and long-lasting project aiming at developing a “Center of excellence” in terms of public and private research and higher education (Tedesco et al., 2017). Although a large part of the territory was urbanized before 1982 (Fig. 19). Land use of the Saclay plateau in 1982 (a) and the land use of the area used in this study (b.), almost 1 400 hectares of land were urbanized since 1982 (Table 19. Land use evolution in Saclay from 1982 to 2021.) and additional urbanization are still projected until at least 2040. Today, most of the remaining farming systems are conventional field crop farms with residual grasslands principally located in the valleys. From 2015 to 2017, main crops were winter wheat (40% of the cultivated area), maize (15% of the cultivated area) and rapeseed (15% of the cultivated area). The remaining arable land was cultivated with a wide diversity of crops, including barley, faba, alfalfa, sugar beet, each representing few percent of the total cultivated area. Soil ecosystem services modelling was carried out at 397 positions of the Saclay plateau, sampled on a regular triangular grid, only in agricultural lands and grasslands present in 1982.

Table 19 : Fr – Land use evolution in Saclay from 1982 to 2021.

Land use	1982	2021
Agricultural	49%	38%
Forest	22%	21%
Urban	25%	35%
Grassland	3%	4%
Water bodies	1%	2%

Figure 34 : FR - Land use of the Saclay plateau in 1982 (a) and the land use of the area used in this study (b).

The scenarios

Climatic scenarios

Two scenarios for climate change were applied in both territories, based on the reference RCPs (Representative Concentration Pathways) proposed by Moss et al. (2010) (Table 20). This was a collective choice made by SERENA partners and more specifically by the intertasks working group on scenarios. The RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 were chosen, the former because it tends to stabilization of GHGs (Greenhouse Gas) emissions by the end of the XXI century and the latter because it predicts an increase of GHG emissions, following no evolution of the GHGs emission regulation.

Table 20 : Fr – The assumptions underlying the different ROIs according to Moss et al, 2010. RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 were considered in this study.

Name	Radiative forcing	Concentration (p.p.m.)	Pathway	Model providing RCP*	Reference
RCP8.5	$>8.5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ in 2100	$>1,370 \text{ CO}_2\text{-equiv.}$ in 2100	Rising	MESSAGE	55,56
RCP6.0	$\sim 6 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ at stabilization after 2100	$\sim 850 \text{ CO}_2\text{-equiv.}$ (at stabilization after 2100)	Stabilization without overshoot	AIM	57,58
RCP4.5	$\sim 4.5 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ at stabilization after 2100	$\sim 650 \text{ CO}_2\text{-equiv.}$ (at stabilization after 2100)	Stabilization without overshoot	GCAM	48,59
RCP2.6	Peak at $\sim 3 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ before 2100 and then declines	Peak at $\sim 490 \text{ CO}_2\text{-equiv.}$ before 2100 and then declines	Peak and decline	IMAGE	40,61

* MESSAGE, Model for Energy Supply Strategy Alternatives and their General Environmental Impact, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, Austria; AIM, Asia-Pacific Integrated Model, National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan; GCAM, Global Change Assessment Model, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, USA (previously referred to as MiniCAM); IMAGE Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment, Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, The Netherlands.

GCMs (General Circulation Models) and RCMs (Regional Climate Models) were parametrized with information deriving from RCP to simulate the response of the climate system to increasing GHG concentrations at regional level. To be useful for our study, a model needs to provide daily information at least on min and max temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), global radiation ($\text{MJ/m}^2/\text{d}$), amount of rainfall (mm/d), wind speed (m/s), vapor pression (mbar) and atmospheric CO_2 concentration (ppm). For France, three combinations of CGMs and RCMs currently provide this dataset for RCP 4.5 and RCP8.5:

- CNRM-CM5_CNRM-ALADIN63 --> named CMRM ALADIN in this report
- EC-EARTH_RACMO22E --> named ECEARTH RACMO in this report
- CNRM-CM5_RACMO22E --> named CNRM RACMO in this report

These 3 climate models were used for both RCP and both sites. The data are published according to an 8 km square grid. The cell chosen was the one containing the higher proportion of the study area. For Naizin, Fig. 35 and Fig. 36 show the comparison of the mean annual rainfall and mean annual temperature projections of the three climate models considering the RCP 4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. The differences between the two scenarios are depicted in Fig. 37 for Naizin and Fig. 38 for Saclay by representing the evolution over time of the mean annual rainfall and the mean temperature from the averaging of the 3 models used for each scenario.

Figure 35 : FR - Evolution of mean annual precipitation for Naizin from 1995 to 2050 according to the 3 climate models used: CNRM ALADIN, CNRM RACMO and ECEARTH RACMO: (A) RCP 4.5 scenario; (B) RCP 8.5 scenario.

A

Figure 36 : FR - Evolution from 1995 to 2050 of the mean annual temperature for Naizin according to the 3 climatic models used: CNRM ALADIN, CNRM RACMO and ECEARTH RACMO: (A) RCP 4.5 scenario; (B) RCP 8.5 scenario.

Figure 37 : FR - Comparison of the annual rainfall (A) and the mean annual temperature (B) at Naizin from 1995 to 2050 according to scenario RCP 4.5 and scenario RCP 8.5. The three climatic models are averaged for a same period over the time period.

Figure 38 : Comparison of annual precipitation (A) and mean annual temperature (B) at Saclay from 1985 to 2050 according to the RCP 4.5 scenario and the RCP 8.5 scenario. The three climate models are averaged over the same period.

Agricultural management scenarios

Change in land and soil management was studied only on the Naizin site. Four different scenarios were established to study the impact of climate and agricultural practice on a number of ecosystem services in response to climate change. These scenarios are presented in Table 21:

- **Business as usual:** the current land and soil management is continued over the period of simulation.
- **Decrease of fertilization and livestock:** corresponding to the European Green Deal, fertilization was reduced by 25% regarding business as usual scenario.
- **Organic Farming:** only organic fertilization derived from livestock effluents and incorporation of grassland into the crop rotation.
- **Energy crops:** the intercrop (mustard) of the business as usual scenario was replaced with rye that is used as energy crop.

Table 21 : Fr - Synthetic description of land management scenarios in Naizin (blue) and of land use scenario in Saclay (green).

Scenario	<i>Business as usual</i>	<i>Decrease of fertilization and livestock</i>	<i>Organic farming</i>	<i>Intermediate energy crops</i>	<i>Urbanization</i>
Study site	Naizin	Naizin	Naizin	Naizin	Saclay
Agricultural practice	Conventional	Conventional	Organic farming	Conventional	Conventional
Fertilization	Mix of mineral and organic fertilizer	Mineral only, 25% less than Business as usual	Organic only	Mix of mineral and organic fertilizer	Mix of mineral and organic fertilizer
Crop rotation	Corn Wheat Mustard	Corn Wheat Mustard	Corn Wheat Grasslands	Corn Wheat Rye	Corn Wheat Rapeseed

			<i>Grasslands</i>		
<i>Description</i>	<i>Current use of the land</i>	<i>Decrease global fertilization by 25% and reduce livestock farming in the site of study.</i>	<i>Rotation and practice coherent with organic farming</i>	<i>Replacement of intermediate crop by fertilized and harvested energy crop</i>	<i>Progressive replacement of agricultural land by urban space</i>

The land management change scenarios were translated into agricultural practices, which were then used as input data for the STICS model. For each land management scenario and each land use that occurs on agricultural soils in Naizin (i.e. crops, meadows and grasslands of the wet valley bottom), crop rotation, fertilisation, tillage, sowing and cutting or harvesting were defined according to Fig. 39. This corresponds to locally dominant crop rotations and cultural practices.

The land management scenarios were applied throughout the modelling period to avoid the problems of transition, which could be more or less abrupt over time depending on regulation or the speed of diffusion of new practices.

Figure 39 : FR - Crop successions and agricultural practices (fertilization, tillage, sowing...) for the four management scenarios and three land uses in Naizin.

Land use scenarios in Saclay

To study the impact of climate change and the interaction of climate and land uses changes two different scenarios were simulated:

- **No change in land use** in which the distribution of cultivated lands, grasslands and urbanised areas observed in 1982 is continued over the simulation period;
- **Land use change** (Fig. 40) in which observed land consumption from 1982 to 2021 and projected land consumption from 2021 to 2050 were considered. Two modalities of land consumption are considered: soil sealing and soil artificialisation (non-sealed soils).

Figure 40 : FR - Land use change from 1982 to 2050 for scenario "Land use change".

The land consumption from 1982 to 2050 was obtained from the *Evolumos* database (Institut d'Aménagement et d'Urbanisme de la région Île-de-France, 2024) that gave the land use at a 25 m x 25 m spatial resolution and at regular time intervals since 1982, *i.e.* in 1982, 1987 1990, 1994, 1999, 2003, 2008, 2012, 2017 and finally 2021. This land use database, specifically developed for following changes in land uses in densely urbanized areas, was chosen because it explicitly differentiated urban open non-sealed areas, *i.e.* parks and gardens, allotments, open spaces for sport, recreation or tourism, from urban sealed areas. The projected land consumption was obtained from the database of the Planning projects of Ile-de-France (Institut d'Aménagement et d'Urbanisme de la région Île-de-France, 2024) (Fig. 41). This database gives zones where urban projects has been planned but specific fields that will be converted in urban use are not specified. To simulate the spread of urban zone, we manually selected fields that change with a 5-year time step. If a crop field is included in a future urban zone, it is changed in "urban zone without soil sealed" at a first step and changed in "urban zone with sealed soil" at a second step. The spread of urban zones is assumed centrifugal from actual urban zones and the balance between the "urban zone with sealed soil" and "urban zone without sealed soil" was kept as much as possible.

Figure 41 : FR - Land use in 2021 and projected urban zones.

The reconstruction of past changes in land use changes and the projection of future changes in land use showed that, between 1982 and 2050, the area of sealed and non-sealed artificial soils increased by ten 10% at the expense of croplands, with the area of grassland remaining relatively stable throughout the simulation period (Fig. 40).

Each land use was simulated by a specific and constant set of land management practices throughout the simulation period (Fig. 42). For cropped areas, a rotation wheat – rapeseed – wheat – maize was simulated. Although the real crop rotations were generally shorter but more diversified, the simulated rotation accurately represented the distribution of the main crops on the Saclay plateau with almost twice as much wheat as maize and rapeseed. The labour and fertilisation practices were derived from Choquet et al. (2021) for wheat and rapeseed and from Chalhoub et al. (2020) for maize (Fig. 42). The simulation of grasslands included the application of 64 Kg N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ in mineral forms and four cuts spread throughout the year. Open urban areas were also simulated as grasslands but with an ecological management involving no fertilisation, a single late cut, and complete removal of the biomass produced. Sealed areas were not simulated, and their supply of SES set to zero.

Figure 42 : FR - Crop successions and agricultural practices (fertilization, tillage, sowing...) for the three land uses in Saclay.

The modelling approach

The Stics crop model

We used the STICS crop model (Baudouin et al., 2022), which was designed to simulate simultaneously crop growth and several soil processes connecting water, nitrogen and carbon dynamics in the soil-crop-atmosphere continuum (Fig. 43). STICS is one-dimensional model with a daily time step for multi-year simulations. It distinguishes multiple compartments of the crop canopy and defines a soil profile with at most five layers. STICS has been calibrated for several crops. It simulates the effect of water and nitrogen stress on leaf area index (LAI), carbon assimilation, aerial biomass, root development and harvest index. Evapotranspiration and nitrogen uptake are assessed based on the concept of limiting factor between soil supply and plant demand. STICS model is a capacitive type model which based on the water storage capacity (i.e. the difference between the water contents at field capacity and at permanent wilting point). Water percolation occurs when soil water content exceeds field capacity. Nitrogen leaching down a soil profile is simulated using the “mixing cells” concept which accounts for convection and dispersion. Nitrogen dynamics are simulated by distinguishing three compartments of soil organic matter: *i*) the fresh organic matter (FOM) including crop residues and organic amendments, *ii*) the microbial biomass, *iii*) the humified organic matter (SOM) which is devised into a stable and an active compartment. The C/N ratio characterizes FOM, which is derived from the scientific literature and long-term monitoring networks. The nitrogen mineralization from SOM depends on water content and soil temperature and soil potential mineralization rate. This latter variable depends on organic nitrogen content, soil bulk density, clay content, CaCO₃ content, and thickness of the biologically active layer for mineralization (*profhum*). The STICS model also considers agricultural practices like soil tillage, organic and mineral fertilization schedules, weather conditions. A detailed description about the STICS model can be found in Beaudoin et al. (2022). As regard STICS input data, the model requires several parameters, which remain constant throughout each simulation (like textural variables and soil depth) and a set of variables which change over time (like soil water content and groundwater level). For soil variables, STICS requires the C/N ratio, the clay content and the pH of the topsoil layer. For each soil horizon, the bulk density of fine soil, the water contents respectively at permanent wilting point and field capacity as well as their thickness must be provided. The bulk density and these water contents are respectively assessed by expertise and using pedotranfer functions of Roman-Dobarco et al. (2019). Daily or cumulative outputs of the STICS

modelling were then used to calculate the different indicators of the ecosystem services provided by soils.

Figure 43 : FR - STICS simulation design (Beaudoin et al., 2022).

Data management and processing

The modelling grids contain 530 points for Naizin and 397 points for Saclay. At each of these points, one simulation per climate model (3), per RCP (2), per scenario (4 for Naizin, 2 for Saclay) was carried out over the period considered. This amounts to 12,720 simulations over 60 years for Naizin and 4,764 simulations over 70 years for Saclay. It was therefore necessary to have a data pipeline to carry out the modelling, as well as the extraction and processing of the data.

Templates of crop rotations (Fig. 39 and Fig. 42) were used according to the land use of the point. For cropland, 3 templates of crop rotations were designed starting from a different rotation head, randomly distributed with equal probability. This distribution was not reassigned between different simulations and remains constant across all scenarios.

Data extraction was performed in two steps:

- SES extractions from daily raw data to annual value from 01/01 to 31/12 for each simulation.
- The 3 climate model simulations of a point for a similar scenario and RCP to a mean value.

To present synthetic results in this document, all points with the same land use were then aggregated.

The assessment of the ecosystem services from the modelling results

After the modelling process, the STICS model outputs relevant for the calculation of ecosystem services were selected from the hundreds existing outputs. A total of 4 SESs were assessed, using several indicators for 3 of them i.e. primary/biomass production, GHG and climate regulation including carbon sequestration and Hydrological control (Table 22). Assessments were done in two steps: calculation for one year, then aggregation at period (several years) level. The ST sealing was studied for Saclay site only.

Data analysis

For this report, the results of the three global/regional climate models have been averaged. In terms of temporal aggregation, for maps and tables, results have been aggregated to 15-year periods for tables and 5-year periods for figures showing annual means. Results by land use class are the mean and standard deviation of all plots in each category. Results for three main SESs/STs are presented in the main text of this report: Biomass production (converted to energy value), soil carbon storage and water production (water yield: amount of rainwater not evapotranspired).

Table 22 : Fr - List of SESs assessed in France according to climate, land management and land use changes, indicators and formula from STICS outputs.

SES	indicator	Required STICS outputs	Units	Formula for year j	Formula per period
Primary / biomass production	Energy of harvested organs: YE	- <i>rendementsec</i> : biomass of harvested organs (0% moisture) (t.ha ⁻¹)	GJ.ha ⁻¹ .yr ⁻¹	$YE_j = \sum_{i=1}^{nc} \text{rendementsec}_i * k_i$ <p><i>nc</i> number of harvested crops in year <i>j</i> <i>k_i</i> conversion coefficient to energy for crop <i>i</i> (FAO, 2003)</p>	$YE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n YE_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>
	Dry Biomass of harvested organs: DB	- <i>rendementsec</i> : biomass of harvested organs (0% moisture) (t.ha ⁻¹)	t.ha ⁻¹	$DB_j = \sum_{i=1}^{nc} \text{rendementsec}_i$ <p><i>nc</i> number of harvested crops in year <i>j</i></p>	$DB = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n DB_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>
	Provision of water to crops: WP	- <i>ep</i> : daily actual transpiration flux (mm)	mm	$WP_j = \sum_{j=1}^{ndays} ep_j$ <p>For year <i>j</i>; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year <i>j</i></p>	$WP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n WP_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>
	Provision of inorganic N to crops: NP	- <i>demande</i> : daily N requirement of the plant to maximise crop growth (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>cumvminh</i> : daily amount of N mineralised from humus (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>cumvminr</i> = daily amount of N mineralised from organic residues (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>fixreel</i> : actual rate of symbiotic fixation (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹)	kgN.ha ⁻¹	$NP_j = \min \left(\sum_{i=1}^{ndays} (\text{demande}_i), \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} (\text{cumvminh}_i + \text{cumvminr}_i + \text{fixreel}_i) \right)$ <p>For year <i>j</i>; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year <i>j</i></p>	$NP = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n NP_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>
Greenhouse gas and climate regulation including carbon sequestration	Csequestration (CO2 removed from atmosphere): CS	- <i>mstot</i> : Biomass of whole plant(aerial+roots+perennial organs) - <i>GHG</i> : Greenhouse gas emission (CO ₂ +N ₂ O) expressed in CO ₂ eq.ha ⁻¹	eqCO ₂ kg.ha ⁻¹	$CS_j = (mstot_j * Ccontent) - GHG_j$ <p>Year <i>j</i></p> <p>Ccontent: carbon content of the plant biomass expressed in CO₂</p>	$CS = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n CS_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>
	Change in soil SOC: dSOC	- <i>DSOC</i> : change in soil organic C (without residues) between beginning and end of simulation	t.ha ⁻¹ .yr ⁻¹	$DSOC_j = DSOC_j / 1000$ <p>For year <i>j</i></p>	$dSOC = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n dSOC_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>
	SOC stock: SSOC	- <i>SOC</i> : amount of soil organic C (=Chumt+Cb) over the profhum depth (kg.ha ⁻¹)	t.ha ⁻¹	$SSOC_j = SOC_j / 1000$ <p>For year <i>j</i></p>	$SSOC = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n SSOC_j$ <p><i>n</i> number of years of the period</p>

SES	indicator	Required STICS outputs	Units	Formula for year j	Formula per period
Hydrological control	Groundwater recharge: GR	- <i>drain</i> : daily amount of water drained at the basis of the soil profile (mm.d ⁻¹)	mm	$GR_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} drain_i$ For year j; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year j	$GR = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n GR_j$ <i>n</i> number of years of the period
	Water yield: WY (amount of rainfall water that does not evapotranspire)	- <i>Cpluie</i> : daily amount of water added to soil (precipitation + irrigation (mm.d ⁻¹) - <i>et</i> : daily evapotranspiration (mm.day ⁻¹)	mm	$WY_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} Cpluie_i - et_i$ For year j; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year j	$WY = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n WY_j$ <i>n</i> number of years of the period
	Flood control potential by soil water storage capacity: FC	- <i>resmes</i> : amount of soil water integrated on the measurement depth	mm	$FC_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} (\max(resmes) - resmes_i)$ For year j; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year j	$FC = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n FC_j$ <i>n</i> number of years of the period
	Amount of water stock in soil water storage capacity: WS	- <i>resmes</i> : amount of soil water integrated on the measurement depth	mm	$WS_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} resmes_i$ For year j; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year j	$WS = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n WS_j$ <i>n</i> number of years of the period
	Amount of water regulated by soil during flood: FW	- <i>Cpluie</i> : daily amount of water added to soil (precipitation + irrigation (mm.d ⁻¹) - <i>drain</i> : daily amount of water drained at the basis of the soil profile - <i>ruissel</i> : Daily amount of water in total runoff (surface + overflow) - <i>esol</i> : Daily actual soil evaporation flux	mm	$FW_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} (cpluie_i - drain_i - ruissel_i - esol_i)$ For year j; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year j	$FW = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n FW_j$ <i>n</i> number of years of the period
Environmental pollution control	Water quality regulation due to N retention of the soil plant system : WQ	- <i>Lessiv</i> = daily amount of NO ₃ -N leached at the base of the soil profile (kg ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>cumvminh</i> = daily amount of N mineralised from humus (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>cumvminr</i> = daily amount of N mineralised from residues (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>totapN</i> : daily nitrogen provided by fertiliser (kgN.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>fixree</i> : actual rate of symbiotic fixation (kg.ha ⁻¹ .day ⁻¹) - <i>ozomes</i> : amount of NO ₃ -N in soil over the depth profiles (kg.ha ⁻¹)	kgN.ha ⁻¹	$WQ_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ndays} ((Cumvminh_i + Cumvminr_i + totapN_i + fixree_i + ozomes_{(i-1)}) - Lessiv_i)$ For year j; <i>ndays</i> number of days in year j	$WQ = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n WQ_j$ <i>n</i> number of years of the period

Results

Climate Change scenarios

Evolution of the climate

Our study is based on two climate scenarios, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 and under the assumptions of these scenarios, 3 sets of climate projections resulting from different models have been taken into account. Fig. 35 and Fig. 36 show that the climate projections resulting from different models lead for a same scenario to the same general trends by 2050 for both precipitation and temperature, but with significant differences between models, especially for the precipitation projections.

By averaging the three projections for the same scenario, it is easier to see the differences in the projections between the two scenarios and the temporal changes over the study period. These differences are shown for Naizin in Fig. 37 and for Saclay in Fig. 38 and summarised by time period for both sites in Table 23.

The main characteristics of climate change over time are as follows:

For Naizin:

- an average temperature that increases gradually, reaching +0.6°C by the end of the period compared with the initial period. The differences between the two scenarios are small until 2050.
- Precipitation does not change significantly in terms of mean annual rainfall for scenario 4.5 and only increases for scenario 8.5 during the last period from 2035 to 2050.

For Saclay:

- an average temperature that gradually increases, reaching +1°C by the end of the period compared with the initial period. The differences between the two scenarios are small until 2050.
- precipitation does not change significantly in terms of mean annual accumulation and remains of the same order of magnitude for both scenarios.

This analysis of average annual trends needs to be completed by taking into account other climatic variables and a more detailed characterisation of intra-annual variations, in particular the distribution of rainfall between seasons.

Table 23 : Fr – Evolution of mean temperature and mean annual precipitation in Naizin and Saclay for periods up to 2050.

NAIZIN		1990-2005	2005-2020	2020-2035	2035-2050
Mean annual temperature (°C)	RCP4.5	11.57	11.65	12.18	12.20
	RCP8.5	11.57	11.80	11.88	12.49
Mean annual rainfall (mm)	RCP 4.5	865	837	880	859
	RCP8.5	865	834	853	946
SACLAY					
		1982-2005	2005-2020	2020-2035	2035-2050
Mean annual temperature (°C)	RCP 4.5	10.9	11.32	11.52	12.08
	RCP8.5	10.9	11.36	11.54	11.89
Mean annual rainfall (mm)	RCP 4.5	662	682	680	702
	RCP8.5	662	678	666	679

Influence of climate scenarios on ecosystems services

The effect of climate scenarios on the assessment of ecosystem services provided by soils is illustrated by considering only the BAU agricultural management and using three ecosystem service indicators belonging to different service categories: (1) crop yields expressed in energy to express the biomass supply service; (2) carbon storage in soils or changes in stocks to express the regulation service linked to climate change mitigation; (3) water yield as an indicator of the hydrological control regulation service.

The evolution of these three services over time for the two scenarios and for the different land cover is shown for Naizin in Fig. 44 and for Saclay in Fig. 45.

Naizin

The evolution of the energy contained in the harvested organs of croplands is always higher than that associated with permanent grassland, whether wet or not (Fig.44A). In the case of crop rotations, this energy increases progressively over time from a value of around 150 GJ.ha⁻¹.year⁻¹ to 180 GJ.ha⁻¹.year⁻¹. The trend is different for grasslands, with a gradual decline in the energy produced over time, leading to a widening of the production gap with the crop rotations described above. The differences between the simulations according to the two climate scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5 are not significant and only appear significant in the case of grassland at the end of the study period, with higher values of energy produced in the case of scenario 8.5.

Initial carbon stocks in Naizin soils are high compared with the French average of 50 tC.ha⁻¹ for agricultural soils, since they average around 85 tC.ha⁻¹ in croplands and 105-110 tC.ha⁻¹ in grasslands (Fig. 44B). The general trend in these stocks up to 2050 is a sharp and continuous decline for grasslands and a moderate decline followed by stabilisation for croplands. The different trends in these stocks appear to be only slightly influenced by the climate scenarios.

Finally, water yield, which is an indicator of hydrological control ES, is always higher for non-hydromorphic grassland than for crops and hydromorphic grassland (Fig. 44C). For Scenario 4.5, the magnitude of this water yield remains in the same range (from 320 to 430 mm.yr⁻¹) and the differences between land use types are almost constant. For scenario 8.5, the water yield increases sharply from 2035 in all situations, reaching a value of about 500 mm.yr⁻¹ in 2050.

Figure 44 : FR - Comparison in Naizin of the mean evolution over 5-year periods of three ecosystem services considering the agricultural management BAU scenario and the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 climate scenarios: (A) energy of the yielded biomass; (B) soil carbon storage; (C) water yield. Cropland, grassland and wet grassland situations are distinguished, and ES results are averaged over 5-year periods.

Saclay

On the Saclay Plateau study site, crop fields unsurprisingly provided more energy than grasslands (Fig. 45A), probably due to higher fertilization rates, but had lower topsoil organic carbon stocks (Fig. 45B). Cropland also had higher water yields than grassland (Fig. 45C), at least at the beginning of the simulation period, probably due to periods of bare soil during which there was no water transpiration. For both land uses, there was a tendency for energy supply and soil organic carbon stocks to decrease over time, with no change in water yields. No differences were observed between the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios, suggesting that i) the observed changes in energy supply, organic carbon stocks and water yields were not caused by climate change, or ii) the two scenarios had similar impacts. With a temperature increase of 1 to 1.2°C and an increase in precipitation of (17 to 40 mm), the changes in temperature or precipitation induced by RCP 4.5 and 8.5 were indeed of relatively small and similar amplitude, at least by 2050.

The decrease in soil organic carbon stocks in situations where biomass harvests were not balanced by organic matter inputs is a well-known phenomenon that is largely independent of climate change. The greater decrease in organic carbon stocks observed in grasslands is consistent with higher stocks at the beginning of the simulation period. The tendency of energy supply to decrease over time could be explained by a decrease in water or nitrogen supply to plants. However, the tendency of energy supply to decrease both in highly fertilized croplands and in much less fertilized grasslands suggests that such decreases were probably controlled by insufficient water supply to plants. Future study of these two indicators should be helpful in discussing such a hypothesis.

Compared to Naizin, the Saclay plateau showed some similarities but also clear differences. The decrease in organic carbon stocks in both croplands and grasslands, the trend of decreasing energy supply in grasslands, or the similar water yields over time under RCP 4.5 in both croplands and grasslands were among the similarities. However, while the energy supply of croplands decreased in the Saclay Plateau under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, it increased in Naizin. Such an increase in Naizin could be attributed to the carbon fertilisation effect in situations where nitrogen and water are not limited. Given that i) crops are fertilised at higher rates at Saclay than at Naizin, and ii) the carbon fertilization effect was present at both sites, the higher and increasing (at least under RCP 8.5) precipitation at Naizin than at Saclay probably explains the difference between the two sites. When nitrogen and water were abundant, the increased atmospheric carbon content led to an increase in energy supply. Conversely, when water was limited, the carbon fertilization effect had no effect and the increase in temperature increased water demand and decreased energy supply. These opposite trends completely reversed the hierarchy of energy supply among sites, with higher energy supply in croplands in Saclay than in Naizin at the beginning of the simulation period, but higher energy supply in croplands in Naizin than in Saclay at the end of the simulation.

Figure 45 : FR - Comparison in Saclay of the mean evolution over 5-year periods of three ecosystem services considering the agricultural management BAU scenario and the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 climate scenarios: (A) energy of the yielded biomass; (B) soil carbon stocks; (C) water yield. Cropland and grassland are distinguished, and ES results are averaged over 5-year periods.

Spatial variability of climate scenarios

Spatial variability between sites in the same study area is illustrated in the case of Naizin by comparing carbon stock losses (in $\text{tC}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{yr}^{-1}$) for all modelled sites under the two climate scenarios 4.5 and 8.5 (Fig. 46). The maps obtained for the two scenarios are very similar, which is consistent with the previous observation that the climate scenario has a moderate influence on changes in carbon stocks: the overall evolution for both climate scenarios is a significant decrease in carbon stocks (at a rate of $-0.13 \text{ tC}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ for RCP 4.5 and $-0.14 \text{ tC}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ for RCP 8.5), with larger decreases in areas (grasslands and wet grasslands) where initial stocks were high. Differences in carbon stock losses between cropland sites suggest that other factors, namely agricultural management and soil type, may also influence carbon storage over time.

Figure 46 : FR - Change in soil carbon storage in Naizin between 2000 and 2050 for RCP 4.5 (A) and RCP 8.5 (B). The symbol indicates land use and the colour of the symbols indicates soil organic carbon loss.

Agricultural management scenarios applied to Naizin

Four agricultural management scenarios have been assessed for the Naizin study area and are detailed considering climate scenario RCP 8.5 and for cropland only. A comparison of these different scenarios is presented in Fig. 47 for the three ecosystem services selected in this report.

Figure 47 : FR - Comparison in Naizin of the mean evolution over 5-year periods of three ecosystem services considering the RCP8.5 climate scenario and the four agricultural management scenarios (A) energy of the yielded biomass; (B) soil carbon storage; (C) water yield. Mean results for croplands are represented.

Energy of the biomass increases progressively over time for all the scenarios, but with potentially strong fluctuations between successive periods, which are observed for all 4 scenarios (Fig. 47A). The

differences between scenarios are significant, of the order of $20 \text{ Gj}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ between the most productive and least productive scenarios. However, the order between scenarios for this level of production changes over time: for the first 15 years, the *Organic Farming* and *BAU* scenarios appear to be the most productive and the *-25% N input* scenario the least one. Gradually, the rank of the *Organic Farming* scenario deteriorates to reach a level equivalent to that of the *-25% N input* scenario. In 2050, the *BAU* scenario is significantly more productive than the other 3 scenarios.

The ES of soil organic carbon storage decreases throughout the simulation period (Fig. 47B), first rapidly for all scenarios, then much more slowly for the *BAU*, *-25% N input* and *Energy crop* scenarios. The decline continues to be rapid for the *organic farming* scenario, which leads in 2050 to a carbon stock in the soil much lower ($-15\text{tC}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$) for this scenario than for the 3 previous scenarios.

Finally, the effect of any agricultural management scenario on the *Water Yield* ES appears to be weak, the curves being very close to each other and all increasing at the end of the period as already described (Fig. 47C).

Spatial variability of agricultural management scenarios

The spatial variability of responses to the different management scenarios is illustrated by mapping the biomass produced for each scenario over the period 1995-2010 and 2040-2050 (Fig. 48).

For all the scenarios and for all the time periods, the range of the ecosystem service between the sites in the study area is very wide: it varies from 30 to $200 \text{ Gj}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$, whereas the average values previously described were of the order of 140 to $170 \text{ Gj}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$, which shows that the differences in soil properties and initial state have a major influence on the response to the climate and agricultural management scenarios.

In the case of the *BAU* scenario, production increases over time and the differences between sites are moderate, except for a few sites characterised by waterlogging or shallow soils (Fig. 48A&B).

The *Organic Farming* scenario is difficult to analyse, as many sites could not be modelled by the Stics model because they reached conditions that the model considered to be outside its range of validity. These simulation problems explain why so many sites were left without information for this scenario (Fig. 48C&D). These are temporary grassland sites and the analysis of modelling failures in these situations will be continued.

The scenario involving the development of *energy crops* shows a spatial distribution similar to that of the *BAU* scenario and a temporal evolution of the same order, with an increase in production over time (Fig. 48E&F).

Finally, the *25% less N input* scenario shows lower production levels than the *BAU* scenario in both periods, but the spatial distribution and temporal trend is similar (Fig. 48F&H).

Figure 48 : FR - Maps of biomass production expressed in energy under the RCP8.5 climate scenario considering two time periods (1995-2010 and 2040-2050) and the four agricultural management scenarios: (A and B) BAU in 1995-2010 vs. 2040-2050; (C and D) Organic farming scenario in 1995-2010 vs. 2040-2050; (E and F) Development of energy crops scenario in 1995-2010 vs. 2040-2050; (G and H) 25% reduction of N inputs in 1995-2010 vs. 2040-2050.

Land use change scenarios applied to Saclay

Two land use scenarios have been assessed for the Saclay study: (i) The BAU scenario assumes that, over the entire simulation period, the entire area initially under cultivation or grassland is maintained according to the rotations and cultivation practices detailed in Fig. 42. (ii) The Urbanisation scenario considers that over time an increasing fraction of the initially cultivated land is urbanised and is either sealed or remains unsealed and turfed, according to the temporal dynamics described in Fig. 40. The results of the analysis of these two scenarios are detailed in Fig. 49, considering climate scenario 8.5.

Biomass energy remains relatively constant in the case of the BAU scenario (Fig. 49A), but decreases in the later years of the simulation, as observed earlier in the analysis of the climate scenarios for Saclay. In comparison, the urbanisation scenario shows a growing gap in energy production with the BAU scenario as the urbanisation dynamic unfolds over time. The gap between the two scenarios is greatest in the period 2040-2045, as long as the energy produced in the BAU scenario remains stable; this gap then decreases in the last years of the simulation as the energy produced decreases. In the end, the relative decrease in energy produced due to urbanisation (-6%) is smaller than the decrease in agricultural land (-16%).

Organic carbon storage in soils decreases significantly for the BAU scenario over the first 30 years of simulation (Fig. 49.B), then remains approximately constant. In comparison, carbon loss is more pronounced in the urbanisation scenario and increases progressively over time.

Water yield fluctuates fairly widely over time for the BAU scenario (Fig. 49C), depending on climate variability, and drops significantly at the end of the simulation period in line with the drop in rainfall observed for the 8.5 climate scenario. In comparison, water yield fluctuates in a similar way for the urbanisation scenario, but decreases progressively over the years compared with the BAU scenario.

Figure 49 : FR - Comparison in Saclay of the mean evolution over moving 5-year periods of three ecosystem services considering the RCP8.5 climate scenario and the two land use scenarios: (A) energy of the yielded biomass; (B) soil carbon storage; (C) water yield.

Discussion and perspectives

The approach implemented

We have developed a simulation chain that can be used to assess the effect of different climate scenarios or agronomic management scenarios on 12 indicators of ecosystem services provided by soils. This chain can be applied to a set of sites whose soil characteristics and initial situation are described, enabling responses to scenarios to be analysed spatially on the scale of a landscape or a wider area.

This chain did not pre-exist our study, because although previous medium-term simulation work had already been developed, including using the same Stics dynamic crop growth model (Tibi and Theron, 2017; Ellili, 2019; Ellili et al., 2021; Pellerin et al, 2020), the version upgrades of Stics, the need to interface it with a geographic information system to spatialise the input data and new definitions of ecosystem services resulting from work carried out as part of the SERENA programme, have led to new developments that have required extensive adaptation of the existing simulation tools. The time required to adjust and parameterise this processing chain was underestimated, and although it is now operational, the results came too late to be fully exploited in this report, hence the decision to present the results for only 3 ecosystem services, although 12 service indicators were calculated.

One of the original features of the work carried out in France in SERENA is that it considered two contrasting agricultural areas, Naizin and Saclay, in terms of their climatic, soil and agricultural production system characteristics, but also in terms of their agricultural dynamics or changes in land use. The other major original feature is that we have not simply considered an average situation for each of these study areas but have applied the simulations to a regular grid of points, which opens up a very broad field of mapping, as well as detailed analyses of the determinants of spatial and temporal variations, as well as their interactions.

A first synthesis for the Naizin study area

Table 24 provides an initial summary of the differences observed for the 3 ecosystem services between the different climate and agronomic management scenarios, taking into account a reference situation observed at the start of the simulation with the BAU scenario.

This table shows differences in sensitivity of the indicators to the scenarios:

- the two services of carbon storage and water yield evolve in the same way (decrease for the storage, increase for the water yield) whatever the scenario considered and thus seem especially sensitive to the climatic evolutions projected by the RCP4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios by 2050, the differences between these two climatic scenarios being moderate in the study area.
- Changes in the biomass production service appear to be more complex and subject both to climate change and to agronomic management scenarios, resulting in an increase in production for the BAU scenario, but either stagnation or a decrease for the other scenarios.

Table 24 : Fr- Summary for the Naizin study area of the changes observed in 3 ecosystem services by comparing the scenarios studied (climate x agronomic management) with a reference situation defined by the BAU-RCP4.5 scenario: (0) no difference; (+) increase; (-) decrease. means that this result should be treated with caution.

	<i>Reference: BAU- RCP4.5 in 1990</i>	BAU- RCP4.5 in 2050	BAU- RCP8.5 in 2050	Organic Farming- RCP4.5 in 2050	Organic Farming- RCP8.5 in 2050	-25% N input – RCP4.5 in 2050	-25%N input – RCP8.5 in 2050	Energy crops - RCP4.5 in 2050	Energy crops - RCP 8.5 in 2050
Energy in biomass	<i>187 Gj.ha⁻¹.year⁻¹</i>	+	+	0	0	-	-	0	0
Carbon storage	<i>85 tC.ha⁻¹</i>	-	-	- ()	- ()	-	-	-	-
Water Yield	<i>370 mm.year⁻¹</i>	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Perspectives

In this report only three indicators of SES have been considered, but results have been obtained for the 12 indicators presented in Table 22. The analysis of the results will be continued in the short term, in particular to extend the results to all indicators in both study areas, but also to assess the relationships between SES/ST in the form of bundles of SES and ST.

So far, the results of the 3 climate models (CNRM ALADIN, CNRM RACMO and ECEARTH RACMO) have been averaged. Therefore, Fig. 35 and 36 suggest that the differences between the models for a given scenario should be of a similar order of magnitude as the differences between the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 climate scenarios. This needs to be carefully analysed and will be necessary for the calculation of uncertainties.

Furthermore, a crucial step in addressing the issues raised in the SERENA project will be to highlight the effect of soil properties on SES, ST and their bundles. This should provide some answers to the question: are all soil types similarly resilient to changes in climate, land use and land management, or are some inherently better able to maintain service levels?

Finally, the data processing and modelling chain developed in this project is fully operational and could be reused to test other scenarios of change or even to extend the duration of the project.

4.5 Scenario analyses – Ireland

Introduction

This scenario analysis explores the potential to reduce soil compaction in Ireland's arable agricultural land through the adoption of zero tillage (ZT) and cover cropping (CC). Soil compaction, a significant form of soil degradation in Europe and across the globe, negatively impacts soil structure by increasing density and reducing pore space, which hampers plant growth, water infiltration, and ecosystem functioning (Frene et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). In Ireland, compaction is a particular challenge due to its soil properties, environmental conditions, and prevalent land management practices (Creamer et al., 2010). Although several studies have focused on compaction in Irish grasslands (Vero et al., 2014; Emmet-Booth et al., 2020; Bondi et al., 2021; Lepore et al., 2024), large-scale mitigation strategies for compaction in arable lands remain relatively underexplored.

Tillage practices, such as conventional tillage (CT), minimum tillage, and zero tillage (ZT), play a significant role in influencing soil compaction. CT, involving deep mouldboard ploughing, tends to increase soil disturbance, while ZT involves direct seeding without soil inversion. While CT typically alleviates soil compaction in the short term, ZT has been shown to gradually reduce compaction over time (e.g. Grant & Lanford, 1993; Ball et al., 2008; Abid & Lal, 2008; Moebius-Clune et al., 2008; Blanco-Canqui et al., 2010; Mchunu et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2012; Presley et al., 2012; Sekwakwa & Dikinya, 2012; Kahlon et al., 2013; Mloza-Banda et al., 2014; Ordonez et al., 2019; Topa et al., 2021). CC, as part of conservation agriculture, offers additional benefits by enhancing soil cover, organic matter, and biological activity between crop cycles (Kassam et al., 2015). Despite the potential of ZT, its impact on bulk density (BD), a primary indicator of soil compaction, typically unfolds over extended periods and often coincides with initial BD increases before long-term reductions are observed (Phogat et al., 2020). On the other hand, CC has been shown to reduce BD in shorter timeframes (e.g. Latif et al., 1992; Breland, 1995; Sainju et al., 2002; Villamil et al., 2006; Ghafoor et al., 2012; Steele et al., 2012; Premi et al., 2013; Wiesmeier et al., 2015; Haruna & Nkongolo, 2015; Nascente et al., 2015; Haruna, 2017; Demir et al., 2018; Adeli et al., 2019; Haruna, 2019; Ruis et al., 2020; Blanco-Canqui et al., 2021). Given the scarcity of specific Irish data on the effect of ZT and CC on soil BD, this analysis relies on literature-based values for BD reductions. Using BD data from Shahrokh et al. (submitted for publication) as a baseline scenario, the analysis applies average percentage reductions in BD derived from a compilation of studies on ZT and CC, with each practice assessed individually. These average values are used to estimate the potential impact of each practice on soil compaction. As such, this scenario analysis explores how the widespread adoption of ZT and CC could influence compaction across Ireland's arable landscape, using BD as the primary indicator of soil compaction.

Methods

Study area:

The scenario analysis was conducted for arable land in the Republic of Ireland (Fig. 50), which constitutes approximately 10.5% of the country's total land area (CSO, 2023). The majority of arable farming is concentrated in the eastern and south-eastern regions, where soil quality and climatic conditions are more conducive to crop production. In contrast, western areas are less suitable for arable farming due to their harsher conditions, making them more favorable for grassland agriculture, which dominates in those regions.

Figure 50 : IE - Study Area – Arable land of the Republic of Ireland.

Deriving Literature-Based Reduction Values:

A literature review was conducted to address two primary research questions: 1) the impact of transitioning from CT to ZT on soil BD, and 2) the effect of CC on BD values. The assessment of BD changes when transitioning from CT to ZT was largely informed by the synthesis conducted by Blanco-Canqui and Ruis (2018), which consolidated findings from numerous global studies on the effects of tillage practices on soil physical properties. For CC, the analysis drew upon both Blanco-Canqui and Ruis (2018) and Haruna et al. (2020), which provided comprehensive analysis on the changes in BD values by CC across various soil types and climatic regions. Additional studies not originally included in these reviews were also incorporated to improve the robustness of the analysis. Both literature meta-analyses presented varied outcomes, reporting cases where BD increased, decreased, or remained unchanged as a result of ZT or CC practices. For the purposes of this work, only studies that observed reductions in BD—indicative of decreased soil compaction—were selected for further investigation. This narrowed our focus to the potential positive impact of ZT and CC on soil compaction which is usually realised after several years to decades (Blanco-Canqui and Ruis, 2018). Given the lack of consistent patterns in BD reduction by soil type or environmental conditions, as well as the under and overrepresentation of soil types, an average percentage reduction in BD was derived from all relevant studies. The calculated values for BD reduction were subsequently -6% for ZT and -8.5% for CC. The reductions in BD across each study are presented in Tables 25 and 26.

Table 25: IE - Literature values for decreases in BD as a result of ZT. Sources derived primarily from Blanco-Canqui and Ruis (2018) with supplementary data added. Average calculated BD reduction of -6% derived.

Location	Soil type	Bulk Density (Mg m ⁻³)	Decrease in BD (%)	Reference
Kansas, USA	Silty clay loam	1.08 - 1.02	-6	Blanco-Canqui et al., 2010

New York, USA	Silt loam	1.45 - 1.32	-10	Moebius-Clune et al., 2008
South Africa	Sandy loam	1.19 - 1.15	-3	Mchunu et al., 2011
Kansas, USA	Silt clay loam	1.38 – 1.28	-8	Presley et al., 2012
Kansas, USA	Silt clay loam	1.52 – 1.44	-6	Presley et al., 2012
Kansas, USA	Silt clay loam	1.53 -1.46	-5	Presley et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Clay loam	1.30 – 1.26	-3	Kumar et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Clay loam	NA	-5	Kumar et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Clay loam	NA	-8	Kumar et al., 2012
Scotland	Clay loam	1.24 – 1.12	-11	Ball et al., 2008
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	1.35 – 1.31	-3	Kumar et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	NA	-8	Kumar et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	NA	-3	Kumar et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	NA	-6	Kumar et al., 2012
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	1.56 -1.49	-5	Ussiri et al., 2009
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	1.6	-7	Ussiri et al., 2009
Malawi	Sandy clay loam	1.51 – 1.34	-13	Mloza-Banda et al., 2014
Saskatchewan, Canada	Clay	NA	-3	Grant & Lafond, 1993
Mexico	Clay loam	1.33	-2	Ordoñez et al., 2019
Botswana	Loam	1.73 – 1.49	-14.9	Sekwakwa & Dikinya 2012
Romania	Clay loam	1.39 – 1.37	-1.5	Topa et al. 2021
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	1.52 - 1.47	-3	Abid and Lal, 2008
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	NA	-4	Kahlon et al., 2013
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	NA	-2	Kahlon et al., 2013
Ohio, USA	Silt loam	NA	-8	Kahlon et al., 2013

Table 26 : IE - Literature sources for decreases in BD as a result of CC. Sources primarily derived from Blanco-Canqui and Ruis (2018) and Haruna et al. (2020) with supplementary data values added. Average calculated reduction of -8.5% applied.

Location	Soil type	Bulk Density (Mg m ⁻³)	Decrease in BD (%)	Reference
India	Clay loam	1.83	-6	Ghafoor et al. 2012
Moldova	Silty clay loam	NA	-14	Wiesmeier et al., 2015
Moldova	Silty clay loam	NA	-15	Wiesmeier et al., 2015
India	Clay loam	1.48	-11	Premi et al., 2013
Nebraska, USA	Silt loam	1.2	-7	Ruis et al., 2020
Norway	Loam	1.21	-11	Breland, 1995a
Kansas, USA	Silt loam	1.27	-3	Blanco-Canqui et al., 2011
Illinois, USA	Silt loam	1.32	-6	Villamil, et al., 2006
Quebec, Canada	Silty clay	1.26	-3	Latif, et al., 1992
Quebec, Canada	Clay	1.28	-4	Latif et al., 1992
Maryland, USA	Silt loam	1.4	-11	Steele et al., 2012
Missouri, USA	Silt loam	1.4	-3	Haruna, 2017
Mississippi, USA	Silt loam	1.44	-4	Adeli et al., 2019
Mississippi, USA	Silt loam	1.34	-3	Adeli et al., 2020
Tennessee, USA	Silt loam	1.3	-12	Haruna, 2019
Goiias, Brazil	Clay loam	1.24	-24	Nascente, et al., 2015
Alabama, USA	Sandy Loam	NA	-7	Sainju et al., 2002
Missouri, USA	Silt Loam	NA	-3.5	Haruna & Nkongolo, 2015
Turkey	Clay	NA	-14	Demir et al., 2018

Deriving Baseline BD Values:

Baseline BD values were sourced from Shahrokh et al. (submitted for publication), which utilised the Irish Soil Information System (Irish SIS) National Soil Map of the Republic of Ireland. This dataset includes both direct measurements of BD and estimates generated through pedotransfer functions in cases where direct measurements were unavailable. Direct BD measurements were obtained from undisturbed soil samples collected from representative profiles, while the best-performing pedotransfer function was applied to unsampled locations based on available soil properties. BD values were clipped to arable land according to Land Parcel Identification System (LPIS) data using QGIS 3.30 –Hertogenbosch. BD values were classified into three groups as per the classification proposed by Bondi et al. (2018). This classification provided a framework for interpreting the relative compaction levels across different regions and allowed for a structured analysis of the potential impacts of ZT and CC on BD reduction in arable land. The groups were as follows:

- **Group 1:** Low BD (< 1.0 Mg m³)

- **Group 2:** Moderate BD (1.0–1.4 Mg m³)
- **Group 3:** High BD (> 1.4 Mg m³)

Baseline BD across arable soils:

Shahrokh et al. (submitted) created the first soil compaction risk map for Ireland, highlighting key regional variations in compaction risk by applying the Bondi et al. (2018) classification of BD and incorporating environmental factors, measured by the number of "untrafficable days" (periods when soils are too saturated for machinery use). Their analysis revealed that soils in the east and southeast—where arable agriculture is concentrated—exhibit higher levels of compaction, primarily due to intensive land management practices. These regions are relatively drier, experiencing fewer "untrafficable days." While this dryness reduces the natural compaction risk, it also creates favorable conditions for more frequent and intensive farming operations, likely contributing to ongoing compaction over time and the prevalence of high BD soils (BD3).

The baseline distribution of BD groups and values, as shown in Fig. 51 A and B, indicate that most arable soils fall within the BD3 category, potentially reflecting a degree of compaction in these areas. These regions are predominantly characterized by Brown Earth soils, which exhibit good drainage, lower clay content, and are primarily loamy or sandy in texture (Creamer et al., 2014). Under natural conditions, these soils tend to have lower BD due to their larger particle sizes and greater pore spaces. However, intensive management practices, such as frequent tillage, have likely increased BD values beyond expected levels for these soil types, indicating a level of soil compaction (Singh et al., 2023). Consequently, intensive agricultural practices are likely the primary driver of soil compaction in these regions, making them a critical focus for investigating potential mitigation strategies. Baseline BD values for the Irish arable soils range from 0.89 to 1.67 Mg/m³, with the majority clustered between 1.40 and 1.63 Mg/m³.

Figure 51 : IE - (A) baseline BD groups according to the Bondi et al. (2018) classification, and (B) Baseline BD values.

BD under Zero Tillage:

By applying the literature-derived reductions to the baseline BD values, new BD values were calculated. Fig. 52A illustrates the resulting changes in BD groupings, as defined by Bondi et al. (2018), under the ZT scenario. While there were no shifts from the moderate to low BD groups, several areas, particularly in southern Ireland, experienced a transition from high to moderate BD. This suggests that these soils are somewhat compacted but could benefit from mitigation efforts, potentially improving soil health and productivity. Under the ZT scenario, the new BD range was 0.84 to 1.57 Mg/m³, with most values clustering between 1.30 and 1.40 Mg/m³, indicating a notable improvement in soil conditions.

Figure 52 : IE - (A) Changes to BD groups under a 6% reduction in BD values under ZT, and (B) Revised BD values under the ZT scenario.

BD under cover cropping:

The CC scenario demonstrated a greater potential to reduce BD values, with an average reduction of -8.5% across all studies. This led to a significant shift in BD groupings, with a large portion of BD3 (high BD) soils transitioning into the BD2 (moderate BD) group. This change was most pronounced along the entire eastern seaboard (Fig. 53A). Additionally, a small area shifted from BD2 to BD1 (low BD), although this change affected only a limited region. Under the CC scenario, BD values ranged from 0.82 to 1.53 Mg/m³ (Fig. 53B), reflecting more favorable soil conditions for the dominant soil types.

Figure 53 : IE - (A) Changes to BD groups under an 8.5% reduction in BD values under CC, and (B) Revised BD values under the CC scenario.

Discussion

The results of this scenario analysis suggest that both ZT and CC have the potential to reduce soil compaction in Ireland's arable lands, as indicated by the reduction in BD values. However, the degree of impact evidently differs between the two practices in the literature, with CC showing a slightly greater potential for BD reduction compared to ZT.

For ZT, the literature derived 6% reduction in BD values primarily shifted soils from the high BD (compacted) category to the moderate BD category, particularly in the southern regions of Ireland. These areas, dominated by Brown Earth soils, are mainly associated with intensive agricultural management practices, which have contributed to the high baseline BD (compaction) levels. Although ZT did not significantly alter the distribution of already low BD soils, the shifts from high to moderate BD suggests that ZT could help alleviate compaction and improve overall soil health over time. However, quite a large amount of arable land remained under the high BD category, which implies that additional measures beyond ZT may be needed to fully address compaction in the most affected areas. In comparison, the 8.5% reduction in BD values under the CC scenario resulted in more widespread shifts in BD groupings, with notable improvements observed along the eastern seaboard. The broader impact of CC suggests that it is a more effective strategy for reducing soil compaction. While quite a large change occurred from the high to moderate BD category, indicating that CC may be effective at reducing compaction, it may not fully restore soils to optimal conditions without complementary practices.

The baseline BD values highlighted that a significant proportion of Ireland's arable land is currently experiencing moderate to high compaction, particularly in regions where intensive management practices dominate. The shifts observed under both ZT and CC scenarios indicate that widespread adoption of these practices could reduce compaction to a moderate level in many regions, especially in the east and south of the country. However, the limited shifts in regions with the highest BD values suggest that long-term or more integrated soil management strategies may be required to further mitigate compaction risks.

Conclusion

Both practices show promise, with CC exhibiting a slightly greater overall reduction in BD and thus compaction. However, this analysis was relatively broad in scope, using average BD reduction values from global literature and assuming that all arable lands are currently managed under conventional tillage without the use of cover crops. In reality, the effectiveness of these practices would likely vary depending on regional factors such as soil type, climate, and the severity of existing compaction. While ZT has been shown to alleviate compaction over time, there are conflicting findings in the literature, with some studies reporting initial increases in BD under ZT before reductions are observed after several years. This delay in ZT's effectiveness highlights the need for a long-term perspective when implementing such practices. In contrast, CC appears to provide more immediate and consistent benefits in reducing soil compaction. However, the combination of ZT and CC may offer synergistic effects, which could be an intriguing area for further research.

The findings suggest that while ZT and CC can improve soil conditions, they may not fully resolve compaction issues in the most severely affected regions without additional interventions. Therefore, for sustainable agricultural practices and long-term soil health, a more comprehensive approach may be necessary, incorporating not just ZT and CC, but also other conservation techniques such as crop rotation, organic amendments, or controlled traffic farming. Further research is needed to better understand the long-term impacts of these practices on Irish soils, particularly through region-specific studies that account for local environmental conditions. Such studies would provide valuable insights and help refine the implementation of best practices for reducing soil compaction and improving soil health across Ireland's agricultural landscapes.

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4.6 Scenario analyses – Poland

Introduction

Climate and land use changes are increasingly affecting soils in Poland, with many negative aspects for agriculture, ecosystem, and overall environmental balance. These two factors are interconnected, with climate shifts in weather patterns and human-driven land use modifications contributing together to soil degradation, erosion, and loss of functions and ecosystem services. Poland is experiencing significant climatic changes, primarily marked by increasing temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns, and the rise of extreme weather events. These changes, driven by global climate trends, have direct and indirect consequences for soils across the country. As temperatures rise, soils become more susceptible for organic matter decomposition. Warmer conditions accelerate the mineralization of organic matter, depleting soils of nutrients essential for plant growth. One of the most visible impacts of climate change on Polish soils is the change in precipitation. While some regions may experience more intense rainfall, others could see prolonged droughts. Heavier rains increase surface runoff, especially on sloped lands, which leads to soil erosion (southern Poland). This process can drastically reduce soil productivity, especially in regions like the Carpathians, where steep slopes are vulnerable to water erosion. On the other hand, droughts are becoming more frequent in certain parts of Poland, particularly during spring, when crops are growing and forming different parts.

In addition to climatic factors, land use changes in Poland are exacerbating soil degradation. Rapid urbanization, deforestation, agricultural intensification, and infrastructure development are some of the key drivers of land use change that are negatively affecting soil threats and their ecosystem services. The increasing demand for food and biofuels has led to the expansion of intensive farming practices. Monocultures, frequent plowing, and the use of heavy machinery compact soils, reducing their ability to retain water and nutrients. In some regions, especially where climate changes occur with poor land management, soils are at risk of desertification. In the future previously fertile lands may become arid and unproductive due to a combination of nutrient depletion, erosion, and loss of vegetation cover.

Methods

Climate change scenarios

For the evaluation of the climate change scenarios we used four time frames: 2018, 2030, 2050, and 2100 and the three Global Circulation Models (GCMs) that were calibrated according to the Polish climate data. These GCMs were as following: (i) MPI-M-ESM-LR, (ii) ICHEC – EC- EARTH, (iii) IPSL-IPSL-CM5A-MR. We used the monthly means for selected timeframes for minimal and maximal temperature, and precipitation. We used the data downloaded from: <https://opendap.4tu.nl/thredds/catalog/data2/uuid/e940ec1a-71a0-449e-bbe3-29217f2ba31d/catalog.html>.

Land use data

For the analysis of the land use changes, we used LUISA data for 2050 to analyse the land use classes changes corresponding to the CORINE Land Cover Level 3 classes. Data was used as a C factor for the soil erosion soil threat and soil erosion control for the soil-based ecosystem service.

Land management data

After the investigation of the data and preliminary analysis of the SOC change according to the different agricultural management practices, we decided to exclude this data due to not achieving any

clear changes for these scenarios. The data used in this part of the task was collected from approximately 500 farms in Poland from 2019 to 2022. In each year farmers provided the information of the cultivation practices, fertilizers used, crops, yields, the area of the field from which we collected sample, and the soil properties of the field.

Modelling of SOC loss, Acidification, and compaction

For this task we used a data on national soil monitoring, the set of static covariates, and the set of dynamic covariates. For the soil monitoring data, we used 41000 points of SOC measurements for mineral soils and 3000 points for organic soils. For the acidification we used 50000 pH in H₂O measurements for mineral soils and 5000 points for the organic soils. For the soil compaction we had only available 1400 points of bulk density measurements for mineral soils and 100 points within the organic soils. The data was measure for the 0-20cm topsoil. The agricultural land in Poland (60% of the area) including arable land and grassland was divided into two groups: organic and mineral soils. For this reason, we used vector soil-agricultural map in the scale 1:25000. We clipped all the variables to the boundary of these soil to prepare two individual models to avoid over- or underestimation on predictive maps due to the big differences in properties between these two groups of soils. For these three soil threats (STs) we decided to apply the digital soil mapping approach using Quantile Regression Forests. We set the model tuning to 15-fold cross validation in 5 repetitions, and number of trees for 500 (200 and 250 were tested for SOC content, however with 500 we achieved the best modelling performance). As the modelling performance evaluation, we calculated ME, MSE, R², RMSE, Ccc, and PCIP. In the latest stage of the modelling, the map of mean predicted value was prepared.

Figure 54. The procedure of modelling SOC loss, acidification, and compaction.

Modelling of Soil erosion by water and Soil erosion control

For the soil erosion modelling we used RUSLE model, according to the cookbook from the T3.2. SERENA EJP-SOIL. For the scenario modelling, the data for R-factor (precipitation) was change from the current (2018) data for monthly sums of precipitation to the predicted values of monthly sum of precipitation for the 2030, 2050, 2100, and two scenarios: RCP 4.5 and 8.5. To combine climate change scenarios with the land use change scenarios, we used LUISA data to assess C-factor. The current state for 2018 was changed to the LUISA data for 2050. For 2030, and 2100, there was no land use changes applied due to the lack of data. Soil erosion control was evaluated as a difference between the erosion calculated with the C-factor, informing about the land use capability to reduce soil erosion, and the state of erosion when there is no reduction of C (C factor =1 for all the country).

Figure 55. The procedures of modelling of soil erosion by water.

Table 27 : PL - The planned STs and SES to be evaluated in the T3.3, D3.4. for Poland.

ST	Planned CC	Evaluated CC	Planned LU	Evaluated LU	Planned LM	Evaluated LM
SOC loss	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
Soil erosion	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Acidification	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Compaction	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
SES						
Soil erosion control	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Climate regulation/C sequestration	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No

Among the planned CC scenarios for ST and SES we did not achieve the evaluation of Climate regulation and carbon sequestration that requires additional work to be done. The results will be presented though in the planned scientific publication. Additionally, we performed the analysis of the changes of Compaction for all the climate change scenarios. For all planned LU scenarios, we delivered results for the Soil erosion and soil erosion control. The rest LU scenarios for the selected ST and SES will be delivered in the scientific paper. For the planned LM scenarios, the results could not be delivered due to the poor quality of the data. We do not intend to include these scenarios in the further work and scientific article.

Results

SOC loss (CC scenarios)

Soil organic carbon (SOC) loss refers to the reduction of carbon stored in the soil, which can be decreased by climate change, land-use changes, and other environmental and man-made factors. The future loss of SOC in Poland was projected using Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), which are scenarios of greenhouse gas concentration trajectories used in climate modelling. RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 represent two such scenarios with different levels of future warming and emissions (Fig. 56).

SOC content – state for 2018

SOC content for 2030 – RCP 4.5

SOC content for 2030 – RCP 8.5

SOC content for 2050 – RCP 4.5

SOC content for 2050 – RCP 8.5

SOC content for 2100 – RCP 4.5

SOC content for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 56: PL - SOC content for 2018, 2030, 2050, and 2100 in RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

SOC content – state for 2018

SOC change for 2030 – RCP 4.5

SOC change for 2030 – RCP 8.5

SOC change for 2050 – RCP 4.5

SOC changes for 2050 – RCP 8.5

SOC change for 2100 – RCP 4.5

SOC changes for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 57 : PL - SOC relative changes in 2030, 2050, and 2100 for RCP 4.5, and RCP 8.5.

Under RCP 4.5, SOC loss is expected to occur at a slower rate than in more extreme scenario, but it will still be significant. Warmer temperatures, moderate changes in precipitation, supported by human land-use patterns can lead to increased decomposition of organic matter, reducing SOC levels. In regions of Poland with intensive agriculture and land use, SOC loss may be more intensive, but agroforestry and grassland areas may help offset some of the losses. The total SOC loss by the end of the century could be moderate, but ecosystem adaptation and carbon sequestration efforts could reduce the severity of the loss. We can observe that the biggest changes will be observed within the arable land, where the more intensive agriculture is observed. The biggest peak in the SOC changes is predicted to occur in 2050 in both scenarios, but for RCP 8.5, the SOC loss will intensify significantly in the loess plateau in Lubelskie region (south-east of Poland). This area is also endangered with water erosion due to the high soil erosivity. This is why within this area, permanent crops, pastures or agroforestry would decrease the occurrence of both threats. In general, it was predicted that the grassland and areas with the occurrence of forests can accumulate more SOC (Fig. 57).

Based on our observations we can conclude that key drivers of SOC Loss under both scenarios are:

- Temperature Rise: Higher temperatures intensify the decomposition of organic matter in soils, reducing SOC levels. This effect is more forecasted under RCP 8.5 due to higher temperature increases.
- Changes in Precipitation: Both scenarios suggest changing precipitation patterns, which can affect soil moisture, erosion rates, and plant growth, all influencing SOC content.
- Land Use and Management: Agricultural intensification, deforestation, and decrease of grassland play a critical role in SOC loss. Within more natural areas SOC loss was predicted to decrease.

Soil erosion (CC scenarios)

Soil loss by erosion – state for 2018

Soil loss by erosion for 2030 – RCP 4.5

Soil loss by erosion for 2030 – RCP 8.5

Soil loss by erosion for 2050 – RCP 4.5

Soil loss by erosion for 2050 – RCP 8.5

Soil loss by erosion for 2100 – RCP 4.5

Soil loss by erosion for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 58: PL - SOC loss by water erosion for 2018, 2030, 2050, 2100 for two scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

Soil loss by erosion – state for 2018

Soil loss by erosion change for 2030 – RCP 4.5

Soil loss by erosion change for 2030 – RCP 8.5

Soil loss by erosion change for 2050 – RCP 4.5

Soil loss by erosion changes for 2050 – RCP 8.5

Soil loss by erosion change for 2100 – RCP 4.5 Soil loss by erosion changes for 2100 – RCP 8.5
 Figure 59: PL - Absolute changes of soil loss by water for 2030, 2050, 2100 in RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

In the RCP 4.5 scenario, in Poland, we assume moderate increases in temperature and relatively stable precipitation patterns after mid-century. Under RCP 4.5, changes in precipitation are less extreme compared to the higher-emissions scenario, but there is still an increase in both rainfall intensity and frequency of extreme rainfall events. Moderate increases in heavy rainfall events will likely increase surface runoff in certain regions, particularly in southern and southeastern Poland, which are already threatened by erosion. There may be an increase in winter rainfall and more frequent storms during the growing season, which could enhance erosion risk, especially on sloped terrains and areas with poor vegetation cover (like maize, beets, rapeseed crops).

RCP 8.5 represents a "business-as-usual" scenario with little to no mitigation efforts, leading to rapid global warming, significant changes in precipitation patterns, and more extreme weather events. Under this scenario, Poland is expected to experience significantly more frequent and intense rainfall events, particularly in the summer months. These heavy storms increase the potential for flash floods and surface runoff, which can result in higher rates of soil erosion. Mountainous and hilly areas in southern Poland, such as the Carpathians, would be particularly vulnerable to soil erosion. The combination of steeper slopes, more intense rainfall, and snowmelt during warmer winters can lead to severe erosion and landslides. The higher temperatures and more extreme rainfall events increase the rate of surface runoff. This runoff can carry away large quantities of soil, especially where the soil structure is weak, or land cover is insufficient to prevent erosion. The overall risk of soil erosion is expected to be higher under RCP 8.5 due to the combination of increased precipitation, more frequent extreme weather events, and higher temperatures. Areas already vulnerable to erosion would be even more affected to these changes (Fig. 58 and 59).

We assume that the key drivers of soil erosion by water in RCP 4.5 and 8.5 will be undoubtedly rainfall intensity and frequency. They are primary factors in driving soil erosion by water in Poland. Higher rainfall intensity leads to increased runoff, which can transform more soil masses. Both scenarios project increases in heavy rainfall events, but RCP 8.5 shows more extreme changes. In general, we can expect significant changes in the mountain areas due to the increase in precipitation and intensive rainfall (Fig. 59).

As a further correction, we will implement the total changes within soils according to the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. This means that except R-factor, also K factor must include the SOC content modelled for each of the scenarios. We assume that the soil texture will not change significantly, hence the sand, silt, and clay content will remain the same as for 2018. For 2030, will be applied for the most accurate Corine land cover (for the 2024), for 2050 we will use LUISA data. Since for 2100 there is no data on land cover, we will not include land use changes.

Acidification (CC scenarios)

Poland, due to the domination of sandy soil, for many years struggles with acidification. Soil pH, which measures the acidity or alkalinity of the soil, is a crucial factor affecting soil fertility, nutrient availability, and overall ecosystem health. This soil parameter is also important to provide a stable condition for plant growth. Climate change, as projected under different greenhouse gas concentration scenarios such as RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, can influence soil pH through changes in temperature, precipitation patterns, and atmospheric CO₂ levels. In Poland, soil pH is expected to change under these scenarios due to the interrelations of these factors.

pH – state for 2018

pH in H2O < 5.00 5.00 - 6.00 6.01 - 7.00 7.01 - 7.50 > 7.50

pH in H2O < 5.00 5.00 - 6.00 6.01 - 7.00 7.01 - 7.50 > 7.50

pH for 2030 – RCP 4.5

pH for 2030 – RCP 8.5

pH in H2O < 5.00 5.00 - 6.00 6.01 - 7.00 7.01 - 7.50 > 7.50

pH in H2O < 5.00 5.00 - 6.00 6.01 - 7.00 7.01 - 7.50 > 7.50

pH for 2050 – RCP 4.5

pH for 2050 – RCP 8.5

pH for 2100 – RCP 4.5

pH for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 60 : PL - pH in H₂O for 2018, 2030, 2050, 2100 under two scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

pH in H₂O ■ < 5.00 ■ 5.00 - 6.00 ■ 6.01 - 7.00 ■ 7.01 - 7.50 ■ > 7.50

pH – state for 2018

pH change for 2030 – RCP 4.5

pH change for 2030 – RCP 8.5

pH change for 2050 – RCP 4.5

pH changes for 2050 – RCP 8.5

pH change for 2100 – RCP 4.5

pH changes for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 61 : PL - pH changes between the actual state and 2030, 2050, 2100 for RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

The general pattern of pH changes is turning into diversification of Polish agricultural soils according to the climate changes. More acidic soil will be furtherly endangered of acidification. pH is predicted to decrease within these areas. From the other hand, soils, where pH was higher will be the least likely to decrease pH in water (Fig. 60 and 61).

Under RCP 4.5, moderate increases in rainfall may enhance leaching, the process by which water removes soluble substances from the soil. Increased leaching of basic cations (such as calcium, magnesium, and potassium) could lead to a gradual acidification of soils, particularly in areas with sandy soils and high rainfall (e.g., southern Poland). Soils that are naturally more acidic, such as those found in eastern Poland, might experience a slight decline in pH as acidification processes intensify with increased leaching. Warmer temperatures can stimulate microbial activity in the soil, potentially increasing the breakdown of organic matter and releasing organic acids, which may also lower the pH. However, these changes are difficult to prove, hence we include them as a potential explanation for the changes that were predicted. Under RCP 4.5, soil pH in Poland is expected to decrease in many regions of eastern and southern Poland due to increased leaching, CO₂ additions, and enhanced microbial activity. However, the changes due to adaptive management practices, such as liming and proper soil management, can help mitigate these effects (Fig. 60 and 61).

In Poland for RCP 8.5 scenario temperature and precipitation changes are expected to have a slightly more impact on soil pH. Under RCP 8.5, increased rainfall intensity and frequency, especially during extreme weather events, would accelerate leaching, leading to a more significant loss of base cations from soils. This process is likely to cause stronger acidification of soils, particularly in areas with already acidic soils or regions that receive heavy rainfall, such as parts of southern and eastern Poland. Soils that are poorly buffered (i.e., have low cation exchange capacity) will experience more rapid and severe declines in pH (sandy soils in central and eastern Poland). The higher temperatures projected under RCP 8.5 will lead to faster rates of organic matter decomposition, releasing more organic acids into the soil. This process would further lower soil pH, particularly in agricultural areas where organic matter is abundant (Fig. 60 and 61).

In summary, soil pH in Poland is expected to decline under both RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios, but the rate and severity of acidification will be higher under RCP 8.5. Effective soil management and mitigation efforts will be critical in maintaining soil health, particularly for sandy soils in agricultural areas in Poland.

Compaction (CC Scenarios)

Soil compaction refers to the process by which soil particles are pressed together, reducing pore space and making it harder for air, water, and roots to move through the soil. Compacted soils have reduced permeability, difficulties in plant growth, and lower soil health. Climate change can increase soil compaction due to changes in precipitation and temperature.

Bulk density – state for 2018

Bulk density for 2030 – RCP 4.5

Bulk density for 2030 – RCP 8.5

Bulk density for 2050 – RCP 4.5

Bulk density for 2050 – RCP 8.5

Bulk density for 2100 – RCP 4.5

Bulk density for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 62 : PL - Bulk density for 2018, 2030, 2050, 2100 for RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

Bulk density – state for 2018

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Bulk density change for 2030 – RCP 4.5

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Bulk density change for 2030 – RCP 8.5

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Bulk density change for 2050 – RCP 4.5

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Bulk density changes for 2050 – RCP 8.5

Bulk density changes for 2100 – RCP 4.5

Bulk density changes for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 63 : PL - Bulk density changes between 2018 and 2030, 2050, 2100 under scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

In RCP 4.5, moderate increases in precipitation could lead to more frequent soil saturation events, especially in the spring and fall. Saturated soils are more likely to compact, particularly in agricultural fields, where machinery use is common. When the soil moisture is higher, the risk of compaction from tractors and other heavy machinery is heightened, as wet soils are more susceptible to being compressed. Under RCP 4.5, in areas where soil dries out due to temperature increases, crusting of the soil surface can occur, which contributes to compaction. Soil drought is a problem nowadays, in the future, due to the increase in temperatures, it may worsen. Moderate warming in RCP 4.5 may lead to some drying of the soil, particularly in the summer months, which could result in surface hardening and compaction in some regions. However, these effects will likely be less severe than under RCP 8.5. In Poland, the reduction in freeze-thaw cycles under RCP 4.5 could contribute to increased soil compaction over time. Freeze-thaw cycles naturally loosen soil by creating expansion and contraction processes. In the winters, leaving ploughed bare soil was a practice for water storage and make soil structure better. With milder winters, the number of these cycles may decline, potentially leading to more compacted soils. This problem will be more intensive in the southern and eastern Poland (Fig. 62 and 63).

Under RCP 8.5, extreme precipitation events are expected to become more frequent and intense, leading to prolonged periods of soil saturation. In southern and central Poland, where agricultural activities are intense, frequent saturation could cause significant compaction, making soils harder to work and reducing their permeability. Waterlogging of soils may also lead to secondary compaction, where layers of the soil become denser over time. Under RCP 8.5, the projected increase in temperature will lead to faster soil drying during heatwaves, particularly in the summer months. This can cause soils to become hard and compacted as they dry out and form crusts on the surface. Over time, this reduces soil porosity and root penetration, contributing to soil degradation. The extreme fluctuations between heavy rainfall and prolonged dry periods create a cycle of wetting and drying that can increase soil compaction. The alternation between these conditions, especially in the eastern

lowlands and agricultural plains, can lead to significant structural changes in the soil, making it more compact and less productive. In the RCP 8.5 scenario, milder winters will further reduce the number of freeze-thaw cycles, particularly in northern and eastern Poland. As mentioned earlier, freeze-thaw cycles naturally loosen the soil, and their absence leads to progressively compacted soils, especially in regions with the harshest winters (Fig. 62 and 63).

Northeast Poland, including regions such as Podlaskie and Warmian-Masurian Voivodeships, has extensive areas of sandy and loamy soils. Sandy soils are more susceptible to compaction because they have larger particles and less organic matter, leading to lower natural resistance to pressure. Once compacted, these soils are more difficult to restore compared to heavier clay soils. Many soils in the northeast are relatively low in organic matter (Fig. 53), which plays a key role in maintaining soil structure and preventing compaction. Low-organic soils are more likely to compact when exposed to external pressure, such as machinery or livestock, especially under wet conditions. For these regions in the last decades, more harsh winters and precipitation occurred. Climate changes, especially the increase in temperatures may have a crucial role in soil compaction (Fig. 63).

Soil erosion control

Soil erosion control – state for 2018

Soil erosion control for 2030 – RCP 4.5

Soil erosion control for 2030 – RCP 8.5

Soil erosion control for 2050 – RCP 4.5

Soil erosion control for 2050 – RCP 8.5

Soil erosion control for 2100 – RCP 4.5

Soil erosion control for 2100 – RCP 8.5

Figure 64 : PL - Soil erosion control (soil masses not eroded) for 2018, 2030, 2050, 2100 under two CC scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

Soil erosion control – state for 2018

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Soil erosion control change for 2030 – RCP 4.5

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Soil erosion control change for 2030 – RCP 8.5

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Soil erosion control change for 2050 – RCP 4.5

relative change [%] ■ < -10.00% ■ - 10.00 - - 5.00 ■ - 4.99 - 5.00 ■ 5.01 - 10.00 ■ > 10.00

Soil erosion control changes for 2050 – RCP 8.5

Soil erosion control change for 2100 – RCP 4.5 Soil erosion control change for 2100 – RCP 8.5
 Figure 65 : PL - Soil erosion control changes between 2018 and 2030, 2050, and 2100 under two CC scenarios RCP 4.5 and 8.5.

Soil erosion control in Poland under RCP 4.5 (moderate emissions) and RCP 8.5 (high emissions) scenarios would see notable shifts due to the combined effects of climate change and land use changes, as projected by LUISA (Land Use-based Integrated Sustainability Assessment). These shifts will force the necessity of changes in erosion control strategies to address the evolving environmental challenges. For 2030, we observe low changes in soil erosion control due to only climate changes. For 2030 we did not apply any land use changes scenarios, hence these changes are linked only to the changing climate. We observe that for central and southern Poland, soil erosion control is predicted to decrease. For RCP 8.5 these changes will be also negative for eastern Poland (Fig. 64 and 65). The LUISA model suggests greater urban expansion, with more land conversion to agriculture, but less attention to sustainable practices. Increased deforestation and land degradation are likely as agricultural demands grow and climate policies are less stringent. For Poland we observe the increase of the areas of permanent crops, orchards, and other plantations. For these regions, soil erosion control is better in 2050 for both scenarios. Under RCP 4.5, soil erosion control would focus on sustainable management and ecosystem-based approaches. Since climate change effects are more moderate and there is a focus on balancing economic development with environmental conservation, soil erosion control would aim to mitigate increased rainfall intensity and land use pressure. Soil erosion control will focus on sustainable land management practices, such as agroforestry, reforestation, and green infrastructure. The emphasis will be on balancing environmental conservation with economic development, using natural solutions to reduce erosion risks. In this “more balanced” and “environmental friendly” climate change scenario we observe spotted areas of the increase of soil erosion control in central, eastern Poland, and mountain regions. This is linked due to the increase of the areas permanently covered with vegetation (grassland, orchards, gardens, permanent crops). Due to the climate changes, we observe that erosion control will be lower in north-west Poland, and only get worse for 2100 (Fig. 64 and 65).

In the RCP 8.5 scenario, Poland will experience much more severe climate impacts, including more frequent and intense storms, higher temperatures, and prolonged droughts, which will aggravate soil

erosion. The land use changes will be driven by greater urbanization and deforestation, as agricultural expansion accelerates to meet food demand. Soil erosion control will need to rely on more intensive and possibly more engineered solutions. More severe climate impacts will require intensified erosion control measures, including hard-engineering solutions like retaining walls, stormwater infrastructure, and riverbank stabilization projects. Unsustainable land use changes, urban sprawl, and deforestation will force to make more complicated and costly interventions to manage erosion risks. For 2050, in RCP 8.5 it is predicted to appear the same patterns as in RCP 4.5 (batter erosion control for areas with the permanent vegetation cover), however we can notice that the other areas, especially central Poland can have less availability for soil erosion control. More doubts have an RCP 8.5 scenario projection for soil erosion. It was predicted that the erosion control will be better for most of the country. This result requires further research to triple check the process of modelling (Fig. 64 and 65). In general, soil erosion control, that is influenced mostly by the land use changes, will be decreasing. We observe that both climate changes and the prediction of land use changes are negative for Poland, hence a special action on soil protection must be applied to save our natural resources.

Conclusions

- 1) Scenario modelling of Soil Threats (STs) and Soil-based Ecosystem Services (SEs) is a challenging task requiring the performance of multiple analyses and testing. The first analyses for Poland can indicate the directions of the evolution of STs and SEs. However, in the further analyses, the more extensive process should be done. This includes: (i) comparing different models using the same data and indicators, (ii) comparing different model tuning parameters within DSM approach, and (iii) application of extensive statistics.
- 2) For the Climate regulation and carbon sequestration SEs we will apply the analysis of multiple indicators (NEP, SOC stocks, CEC) to evaluate the soil potential for the C sequestration. This requires additional time and computation; hence these results will be presented in the article about SERENA EJP-SOIL scenarios work on STs and SEs for Poland.
- 3) We wish to warn that climate changes will influence all of the analysed STs and SEs. This means, that the Polish Government and local authorities may implement special regulations on soil protection and land management.

Take-home messages for stakeholders:

- 1) Among all soil threats and soil-based ecosystem services we predicted that the biggest threat that may occur within the agricultural soil in Poland is SOC loss. For every modelled scenario, SOC loss will be the highest for the arable land, and the part of Poland currently being under the most intensive agriculture. To protect soils, more grassland should be restored. We predicted that within grasslands, SOC will be increasing. This may be one of the solutions to solve SOC loss problem within the agricultural land.
- 2) Land use has a crucial impact on STs and SEs changes. More analysis should be performed using this data. LUISA data is sufficient for the general analysis, but to indicate regional or local problems, more accurate data should be prepared and modelled, using for example datasets from CORINE Land Cover.

- 3) Soil compaction and acidification may become the biggest problem in the eastern part of Poland, hence, modern agricultural practices, such as strip tillage, cover crops, and application of calcium carbonate should be applied.

